

Roadmaps, White Paper and Value Added Reports v2

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Executive Summary

This second edition in the EU-CIP Roadmap and Value-Added Report series builds upon the foundation established in the initial report, delivering updated insights and a broader strategic perspective on the evolving landscape of Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) in Europe.

The primary aim of this report is to provide stakeholders—including policymakers, industry leaders, researchers, and critical infrastructure operators—with a clear, actionable overview of the current status, emerging trends, capability gaps, and future needs within the CIP/CIR domain. By employing an iterative and consultative methodology, this series ensures that each edition reflects the latest developments and stakeholder feedback, supporting evidence-based decision-making and strategic planning.

Key highlights of this report include:

- **An enhanced analysis of the CIP/CIR landscape**, offering a more comprehensive and strategic view that builds on previous findings and incorporates new research outcomes, stakeholder input, and sectoral developments.
- **Identification and assessment of existing gaps and needs**, providing actionable intelligence for guiding future research, innovation, and policy initiatives.
- **A streamlined structure**, designed to serve as a reference point for all future roadmap documents and to facilitate ongoing knowledge sharing within the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub.
- **Detailed annexes**, which offer in-depth exploration of research outcomes and further contextualize the main findings presented in the report.

While this report continues to focus primarily on EU research and innovation activities, it marks a shift from a microscopic examination of individual projects to a more strategic, holistic view of the CIP/CIR ecosystem. This approach enables a deeper understanding of sector-wide challenges and opportunities, and supports the development of targeted roadmaps, white papers, and value-added reports that will inform and shape the future of critical infrastructure security and resilience in Europe.

Looking ahead, future editions will continue to refine and expand this landscape, providing the CIP/CIR community with timely, relevant, and practical insights to drive innovation, collaboration, and preparedness across the sector.

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Definitions and acronyms

BCDR	Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery
BYOD	Bring Your Own Device
Co-16	Capability
CA	Consortium Agreement
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CBRNE	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear, and high yield Explosives
CER	Critical Entities Resilience (Directive)
CG1-15	Capability Gap
CI	Critical Infrastructure
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
CIR	Critical Infrastructure Resilience
COVID19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
C/P	Cyber/Physical
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECSCI	European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
ISM	Information Security Management
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISO/TC	Technical Committee within the ISO
NIS, NIS2	Directive on security of network and information systems
OT	Operational Technology
PC	Project Coordinator
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SIPS	Sensitive Industrial Plants and Sites
SC	Scientific Coordinator
TM	Technical Manager
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
USD	US Dollar
VC	Venture Capital

1. Introduction

1.1. The roadmap for the “EU-CIP journey”?

Every successful journey begins with a clear plan—and the EU-CIP roadmap is exactly that: a strategic guide designed to chart the course for advancing Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience (CIP/CIR) across Europe. This roadmap provides a structured, transparent, and actionable framework for researchers, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the broader community to follow, support, and implement.

To ensure the EU-CIP roadmap is both credible and practical, it is essential to answer some fundamental questions—much like planning any important journey:

- **What is our destination?** What are the ultimate goals we want to achieve for CIP/CIR in Europe?
- **Who are the travellers?** Who are the key stakeholders and contributors on this journey?
- **What resources do we have—and what do we need?** How much time, expertise, and support are available to reach our objectives?

By clearly defining these elements, the roadmap becomes more than just a plan—it becomes a living tool that guides collective action, aligns resources, and measures progress. In the following sections, we outline the main components of the EU-CIP roadmap and provide an update on how each is being developed and implemented.

1.2. Defining the roadmap objectives, requirements and scope: The work in progress

Answering the above questions affects the objectives of the roadmap and, especially in practical and precise terms for the area of CIP, is a difficult task. The trip towards “safe/well-protected and resilient infrastructure” is a difficult journey, especially because of the area itself. Despite the existence of the CER (Critical Entities Resilience) and NIS (Network and Information Systems) Directives, their application is subject to member states’ interpretation, often leading to different decisions and application scopes at the national or regional level.

An important note is that one should distinguish between the objectives and scope of the EU-CIP project and the EU-CIP roadmap – this document addresses, obviously, the roadmap.

The current state of the work on the objectives and the scope of the roadmap is characterized by the following elements:

1. Long-Term Vision:

In general terms, the long-term vision is well defined in EU-CIP. It is well defined in the proposal and reiterated in this version of the roadmap document.

2. Clear Objectives and Goals:

The EU-CIP Roadmap objectives are still to be defined more precisely. Currently, they are still generic ("improve CIP/CIR"), very generally defined and still not unmeasurable or quantifiable. Hence, the EU-CIP project should help articulate both the overall objectives and goals of the project's research, and the practical tangible objectives of individual actions. The achievements of specific outcomes should be verifiable, supported by data and feedback by the intended users/beneficiaries of the results.

3. Well-Defined Scope:

As the fields of interest do not have clear boundaries, defining the scope is also a challenge, but the clearly identified boundaries of the scope of the EU-CIP research have to be defined. A clearly defined scope should include limitations or delimitations in order to manage the respective expectations well and to ensure that the research proposed in the roadmap is feasible within the given constraints. The following versions of the roadmap should address this issue in more detail, based also on the feedback from the potential/expected users and implementers.

4. Evaluation and Monitoring, including Criteria and Indicators:

EU-CIP has defined how the project will measure success in terms of measurable criteria and monitoring plan. The key performance indicators framework has been defined in the public deliverable D2.1 .

5. Further elements to be considered, and some of them still "work-in-progress" in EU-CIP are:

- **Timeline:** the overall one and the time estimates for each phase. (Still to be done).
- **Prioritization** of tasks, activities, and milestones in the roadmap. (Still to be done).
- **Resources**, including the budgets, tools, equipment, and personnel needed, as well as an overview of what we have, and what do we still need to acquire? (Still to be done).
- **Methodology** to be used. This should recognize and include the "dynamic/living" character of the EU-CIP roadmap: especially the CIP/CIR research which involves a great deal of iteration, revisiting, and refining the approach based on findings.
- **Flexibility** means acknowledging that the context of CIP/CIR might (and probably) will change, therefore requiring room left for adjustments and unexpected turns (Embedded in the current EU-CIP concept).
- **Roadmap risk assessment** involves identifying potential challenges or obstacles. (Still to be done).
- **Collaboration of the key stakeholders** and how will they engage. This aspect is to be improved in further work – currently there is an uneven focus on the stakeholders coming from the research side.
- **Roadmap communication plan**, which shows how the proposals, and the results of the roadmap will be communicated and through what channels. The efficient feedback mechanisms need to be foreseen. This is an aspect that still needs to be improved upon in further work – there is currently an uneven focus on the stakeholders coming from the research side, while the role of the EU and national

- bodies should be emphasized in the future. The feedback mechanisms should be further elaborated and a system for receiving and incorporating feedback established.
- **Ethical considerations** should not be forgotten, as they become critical for the CIP/CIR, e.g., due to “lost/decay of trust” in the society.

The EU-CIP roadmap should be a dynamic guide that adapts to the twists and turns of the EU-CIP research journey.

1.3. Format of the EU-CIP roadmap

The fact that institutional, national, and industry roadmaps are different does not surprise, but the variety of formats used within the EU does. In the preceding version of the EU-CIP roadmap (*v1*) we had taken strategic roadmaps such as the “European Green Deal – Striving to be the first climate-neutral continent” (https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en), the EU Energy Roadmap 2050 (Impact assessment and scenario analysis) and the Roadmap for transforming the EU into a competitive, low-carbon economy by 2050, as possible leading examples. This was done because these roadmaps directly address the alignment of those aspects relevant for the EU-CIP roadmap, namely:

1. Policies
2. Research & innovation (R&I)
3. Standards
4. Go-to-market strategies and measures (G2M).

In addition, they include issues that would be also relevant to the EU-CIP roadmap, such as cybersecurity, resilience and infrastructures, and propose a concept for the continuous interaction with and monitoring of stakeholders’ needs, market trends, and societal transformation.

Thus, for the EU-CIP roadmap, we have proposed to have a “roadmap-of-4-roadmaps”, dynamically synchronized within the context of the project, as one living document, possibly remaining as such also beyond the project.

Figure 1: EU-CIP Roadmap creation methodology

1.4. Time horizon for the EU-CIP roadmap

The currently considered time horizon for the EU-CIP roadmap is the year 2030. The reason for this choice is defined by two factors:

- The need to include future trends related to the threats/risks and to the development of the protection technologies and resilience concepts (leading to the extension of the time horizon), and
- the need to be pragmatic, realistic, and praxis-oriented (leading to the shortening of the time horizon).

The result, the year 2030, is thus considered to be a reasonable compromise between these two issues.

2. The methodology for identification of the roadmap baseline – identifying and quantifying needs and gaps

2.1. General

The basis/baseline for precisely defining the “goal(s) of the journey” in the EU-CIP roadmap is to be provided by the EU-CIP methodology for the identification and quantification of needs and gaps in the area of CIP. It is envisaged as being “progressive” and “integrative” one and will consider and possibly include all different qualitative and quantitative methods needed for the assessment and integrate them (therefore “integrative”) in a complementary way. The methodology is “progressive”, because we plan to start with simpler qualitative methods and enhance the analysis by more sophisticated and more quantitative methods later on during the course of the project.

The methodology (i.e., the proposed combination of methodologies) within the EU-CIP project should enable reliable analysis (and results) related to the assessment of the dynamics, trends, and opportunities in the area of CIP/CIR. The combination of both qualitative and quantitative methods will play an essential role in gaining a comprehensive understanding. The results should enable the following insights:

- The appropriate time scales with respect to the needs and gaps over different time horizons (e.g., now, in 5 years, and until 2030).
- The stakeholders’ groups and their needs and gaps for, e.g., first responders, governments, analysts, researchers.
- The technical and financial quantification with regards to how big the needs and gaps are, what is the expected benefit of the envisaged solutions, and the costs of solutions.
- A ranking for implementation.

The main qualitative and quantitative methods envisaged for the analysis, with an indication of their application during EU-CIP project, are listed below.

2.2. Qualitative methods

In EU-CIP project, these methods will be primarily used to identify the particular needs and gaps within the CIP/CIR domain, such as, for example, was done during the panel discussion held as part of the EU-CIP/ECSCI conference in September 2023 (see deliverable D5.4 *First Annual Conference on Resilient Infrastructures*).

1. Literature analysis, expert opinions and case observation:

The methods based on literature analysis and case observations are already being applied in EU-CIP project. They allow for the direct observing and recording of behaviour in natural settings. Collection of data in the area of standards and taxonomy has already been performed by means of the EU-CIP FAIR Observatory. The “expert opinions” are yet to be collected within the project. By studying individual cases from the preceding EU-supported and other projects, as presented in reports, websites, or other relevant environments, such actions have been initiated in this document.

2. Surveys and Interviews

The planned interviews have as their goal the gathering of opinions, preferences, and insights from the stakeholders in the area CIP/CIR, primarily from relevant individuals. Even if the results are difficult to discern from the collected information, they give pointed insights into understanding the stakeholders' needs, preferences, and perceptions of needs and gaps. Internal consultation surveys about the current gaps and needs have been launched among the Consortium members. The results from other surveys (done also by means of the Survey tool in the FAIR Observatory) will be included in the Roadmaps, White Paper and Value Added Reports *v3* and *v4*.

3. Focus Groups:

Focus group discussions led by an effective moderator to explore opinions and attitudes can be organized mainly within the actions dedicated to communication and dissemination within the project (e.g., conferences and workshops) and will allow for exploring in-depth reactions to CIP/CIR-related products, services, and research strategies. How and when exactly the focus groups will be organized is still to be planned.

2.3. Quantitative methods

1. Surveys and Questionnaires, including Statistical Analysis:

These are already built in the tools (FAIR Observatory) and enable the collection of numerical data through structured questionnaires. They have already started and have provided the first results, summarized in the D3.3 FAIR Data CIP/CIR Observatory report (Figure 2.1). By segmenting the relevant stakeholders into appropriate groups, the understanding of the needs of particular stakeholders' groups will be enhanced.

2. Stakeholders' Segmentation:

The above tools (i.e., surveys and questionnaires) can be and have been already used for the stakeholders' segmentation.

3. Big Data Analytics:

Analysing large datasets to uncover patterns, trends, and relationships/correlations is essential for assessing complex domains like CIP/CIR. The FAIR Observatory allows one to explore relationships among the data identified based on the semantic analysis of stored information (text) and graphically depicted as a network. This is an advantage for the user as she/he obtains an overview of the related information. Obviously, collecting enough data is a prerequisite for this type of analysis.

3. Sketch of a roadmap to enhance CIP/CIR

3.1. Introduction and Driving Principles

The EU-CIP roadmap for enhancing CIP/CIR in Europe is based on knowledge and insights extracted from the knowledge network of the project. Such insights have been derived based on various modalities, including questionnaires, stakeholders, workshops, and interaction with various EC-funded CIP/CIR projects and initiatives such as the ECSCI network. The collected insights concern scientific and technological development issues, regulatory and standardization issues, policy development updates, as well as the ever-important human factors, including the needs for training and skills development.

The roadmap aims at fostering a new vision for more intelligent, automated, predictive, and collaborative protection of critical infrastructures, which is destined to address recent challenges in the CIP landscape, such as a new range of asymmetric, hybrid, cyber-physical attacks, and the emergence of new vulnerabilities as a result of changes in the geopolitical and technological landscape. Hence, while the roadmap recommends a wide range of individual measures and activities, it also caters for their integration and combination towards delivering wider CIP vision.

Selected activities of the EU-CIP project such as the needs and market analysis can be considered as a starting point of the roadmap, which prescribes activities that are destined to cover identified needs and gaps.

In terms of timeline, the EU-CIP roadmap considers a nearly 10-year timeline in order to provide a CIP/CIR improvement outlook with a 2030 horizon.

In this context, the present roadmap is driven by the following principles:

- **Consistent Vision:** The roadmap is driven by a consistent vision of more intelligent, proactive, automated, and cost-effective CIP/CIR in Europe, which can address modern challenges faced by CIP/CIR operators.
- **Holistic Approach:** The roadmap is developed based on a holistic approach that considers technological, socio-economic, and policy development aspects. It addresses not only the development of innovative technologies for CIP/CIR, but also the advancement of complementary assets (e.g., processes, training, regulations, standards) that could maximize the impact of new technologies on CIP/CIR effectiveness.
- **Knowledge and Data Driven:** The roadmap leverages information and insights from the EU-CIP knowledge network, as well as data collected from various sources. It therefore aims at describing practical, data-driven, and evidence-based measures. First and foremost, the roadmap addresses the CIP/CIR capability gaps that have been identified within the scope of the EU-CIP knowledge network.
- **Research and Innovation Centric:** EU-CIP puts research and innovation at the centre of its analysis activities. Therefore, the roadmap recommends a wide range of research and innovation development activities, acknowledging the fact that innovative solutions can be the answer to some of the most pressing contemporary challenges.
- **Aligned to Market Trends:** Market trends and market analysis are also considered in the development of the roadmap. EU-CIP aims at providing practical recommendations that are in-line with the state of practice and the state of the market, rather than specifying novel measures which are, however, unconnected from the market and the activities of the industrial stakeholders.

- **Continuous Improvement:** The roadmap is developed as a living document in-line with a continuous improvement discipline. This is because the EU-CIP activities that support the development of this roadmap are still in progress.

The initial version of the roadmap is sector agnostic i.e., it includes activities, plans, and measures for all CIP sectors. Nevertheless, EU-CIP is providing sectorial insights as part of the sector specific whitepapers that will be included in subsequent deliveries i.e., *v3* and *v4*.

3.2. Stakeholders' Addressed

The roadmap prioritizes insights and recommendations to the following stakeholders:

- **Policy makers** who develop CIP/CIR related policies, including the European Commission (EC) which leads policy development for CIP R&I (Research and Innovation) in Europe.
- **Critical Infrastructure** operators who are the primary beneficiaries of a more innovative and effective CIP/CIR landscape in Europe and beyond.
- **CIP/CIR technology providers**, including vendors and integrators of innovative CIP/CIR solutions, who are expected to provide the technology enablers of the EU-CIP vision. A prominent position within this stakeholder group is held by high-tech innovative SMEs and start-ups that develop CIP/CIR solutions.

3.3. Roadmap Parts

The roadmap consists of three complementary parts that should be implemented in parallel:

- **Research and Technological Development Roadmap**, which refers to the R&I activities that will be undertaken by the various stakeholders in order to develop the technological enablers that will improve CIP/CIR in Europe in-line with the EU-CIP vision.
- **Regulatory and Standardization Roadmap**, which comprises measures for CIP/CIR compliance to standards and regulations, including activities for enhancing existing standards and regulations.
- **Training and Skills Development Roadmap**, which focuses on the development of the human capital for CI operators and technology providers to allow them to implement and fully leverage the suggested research, technology, and regulatory developments of the other two roadmaps.

The three parts of the roadmap are expected to be executed in parallel, while being aligned and interacting with each other. Note also the three parts of the roadmap will be reinforced by EU-CIP results.

Figure 2: The Three Parts of the EU-CIP Roadmap

3.4. Research and Technological Development Roadmap

The research and technology roadmap includes the following steps:

1. **Needs, Gaps and Market Analysis (2022-2024):** This step is currently carried out within the scope of the EU-CIP project, which has already identified a range of capabilities gaps towards the project’s vision for improving CIP/CIR in Europe. Several of these needs (e.g., CG7 – Development and Deployment of AI-based systems and CG12 - Adaptive Threat Intelligence) relate directly to the development of innovative technologies, while others (e.g., CG5 – Problems with the classification of IoT Devices, CG8 – Lack of Holistic Security Management Systems, and CG13 - Incident Response Coordination) also include technological development aspects. Along with these capability gaps, the project is carrying out market analysis (see a snapshot in the Annex D) that will also drive the technological development roadmap. Specifically, the research and technological development work should pursue areas where there are gaps in the market, yet it will address areas where only non-European solutions exist (e.g., this is currently the case with AI and Large Language Models for security applications) to support Europe’s technological sovereignty in the long term. During 2024, the EU-CIP needs/gaps analysis will be more mature and hence will be considered complete as a first step to the roadmap.
2. **Research Activities to address the Capability Gaps (2021-2025):** As part of this step, ongoing and future research initiatives should focus on researching solutions (TRL between 3 and 6) to the identified gaps. CI operators and technology integrators/vendors should engage with such activities, while policy makers will promote policies that foster relevant research. The design of proper research programmes (e.g., Horizon Europe Calls for Proposals) falls within the policy development activities. Other activities that encourage CI operators to engage with research activities should be considered as well. Moreover, activities that foster stakeholders’ collaboration in research (e.g., co-creation and co-design activities) should also be supported.
3. **Development and Field Validation of Innovative Technological Solutions (2022-2026):** This step concerns the integration of research results on innovative technological solutions that will be deployed and validated in pilot sites and in the field (TRL between 5 and 8). In this step, innovators and technology development stakeholders will be mobilized to engage in these activities, in close synergy with CI operators. Policy makers could also support these

activities based on innovation friendly policies like incentives (e.g., tax cuts), support for access to finance, collaborative innovation programmes (e.g., Digital Europe) and more.

4. **R&I on CIP Integration and Collaboration Activities (Regional, National, EU Levels) (2022-2026):** In parallel to the above-listed research and innovation development activities, there will be a need for strong collaboration and integration of CIP activities towards alleviating silos, fostering the exchange of CIP information and making value chains more resilient. The latter goals can be directly derived from the needs analysis that has been carried out so far, which indicate the need for closer stakeholders' collaboration. A phased approach could be followed in the implementation of related integration and collaboration activities based on their geographical scope. Specifically, integration should be initially pursued at the regional level and gradually expanded at the national and EU levels. As part of the integration and collaboration activities, it is also envisaged that public-private partnerships can be established to foster the implementation of integration activities.
5. **Commercialization of Innovative Solutions and Deployment in Production (2025-2028):** The ultimate target of the research and technological development activities is to end-up with commercial, production ready solutions (TRL 8-9) that can be deployed and fully leveraged by CI operators. In this direction, this step plans for commercialization activities that should be supported by measures that help to move research and innovation results to the market. Relevant activities, including measures for access to finance (e.g., start-ups financing, grant funding, VC funding), support in IP (Intellectual Property) management issues (e.g., patents), as well as support for accessing EU markets.
6. **Continuous Improvement (2027-2030):** The roadmap foresees activities for obtaining stakeholders' feedback in order to improve the R&I and commercialization activities. Based on these activities a continuous improvement cycle will be supported. Innovations deployed by CI operators need to be fine-tuned in terms of functionality, technical and operational robustness, alignment to evolving standards and regulation, and more.

Figure 3: Overview of the Research and Technology Development Roadmap

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

3.5. Regulation and Standards Development Roadmap

The regulation and standards development roadmap includes the following steps:

- 1. Analysis and Assessment (2022-2024):** This includes an analysis and assessment of existing standards and regulations, which is carried out as part of the EU-CIP ANALYSIS work. It creates a catalogue of standards and regulations for CIP/CIR, which is being integrated into the project's knowledge hub and FAIR observatory. Furthermore, gaps and limitations in existing CIP standards and regulations are being identified.
- 2. Regulatory Awareness and Compliance Activities for CIs (2023-2025):** Prior to proposing and developing new standards and regulations, there is a need for assessing the merit and the effectiveness of existing regulations and standards for CIP. CI operators and other stakeholders should acquaint themselves with regulations like the NIS2, the GDPR, and the CER directive. CI operators should plan for relevant activities and policy makers must devise both incentives and penalties for compliance and non-compliance. This step should also collect stakeholders' feedback about the practical application of the various regulations.
- 3. New Standards and Regulations Development Specification (2024-2026):** This step will study and specify the need for new standards and regulations, including fine-tuned versions of existing ones. Regulatory and standardizations gaps will be addressed in areas like security information sharing, the inability to address emerging vulnerabilities and threats, the lack of standards and regulations for international cooperation, and so forth. Likewise, the need for introducing new standards should be documented, such as standards needed due to the adoption and deployment of novel technologies (e.g., new forms of AI, biometrics, blockchain). The standards and regulations to be specified will be streamlined with the research and technological development activities of the previous roadmap, to ensure that the standardization processes can support the adoption and technological longevity of the technology enablers of the EU-CIP vision.
- 4. CIP Standards Development Processes (2024-2028):** This phase involves the development of the identified new standards and regulations by relevant regulators and SDOs (Standards-Development Organizations). The process will leverage specifications from the previous step and will carry out relevant consultation, validation, fine-tuning and final approval processes. Recommendations to relevant organizations for specific types of standards shall be provided, along with incentives for them to support the process.
- 5. Continuous Improvement and Fine-Tuning (2027-2030):** The roadmap foresees activities for the continuous improvement of the standardization and regulatory development processes.

3.6. Training and Skills Development Roadmap

The training and skills development roadmap includes the following steps:

- 1. Skills Gap Analysis, Skills Profiles Identification, and Goal Setting (2022-2024):** This is a first step of the roadmap that is already being carried out by the EU-CIP project as part of its training activities. The project has produced a catalogue of 100+ (existing) CIP/CIR related courses, while it has also identified training as one of the main capability needs/gaps expressed by CI operators and CIP/CIR vendors. Several of the identified gaps are cybersecurity related, while the need for training and upskilling CI employees in emerging technologies is also expressed

(e.g., see for example CG11 – Poor Awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges, EU-CIP will specify the skills profiles that will be required to support the envisaged CIP/CIR improvements. These profiles will be documented in upcoming deliverables and whitepaper available in the project Knowledge Hub. Likewise, learning paths will be identified along with some envisaged goals regarding the number of CIP/CIR professionals that should be reskilled.

- 2. Training Resources Development (2023-2026):** This phase of the roadmap will deal with the development of the required learning resources to support skills development in areas and ways that cover the identified gaps. The training resources to be developed will include training programmes, courses, practical assignments, and certifications, among other actions. In this direction, resources that fill specific gaps and programmes that fulfil certain learning paths will be developed. Training organizations, education providers, and the human resources departments of CI operators and CIP/CIR solutions vendors will be mobilized and incentivized in this process. EU-CIP is already contributing to the development of training resources, aiming to provide examples of the type of resources needed and of their role in the upskilling process. However, it is acknowledged that the resources developed in EU-CIP will by no means be adequate to support the breadth and depth of the required development of training resources.
- 3. Training Delivery – Reskilling and Upskilling Programs Delivery (2024-2027):** This phase of the roadmap shall emphasize the delivery of the programmes and other resources developed towards realizing the upskilling and reskilling processes required for the future of CIP/CIR. The delivery shall be planned in-line with the set goals in the first version of the roadmap (e.g., towards reskilling a specific % of CI professionals at the EU level). Policy makers must develop policies (e.g., incentives, training programmes, awareness raising programmes, funding programmes) that support the delivery of the required reskilling and upskilling programs. CI operators and CIP/CIR solutions vendors/integrators shall be supported in their engagement in the upskilling and reskilling processes as part of their human capital development strategies.
- 4. Progress Tracking – Adjustments – Fine Tuning (2027-203):** A fine tuning process shall be implemented as part of this step of the roadmap. It entails the tracking of the upskilling/reskilling progress and its assessment against the set goals at organizational, regional, national and EU levels. Moreover, stakeholders' feedback must be obtained. Stakeholders feedback and the outcomes of the assessment will be used accordingly to adjust and fine tune the educational, training and upskilling processes. The fine tuning may lead to the development or fine-tuning of training resources, the structuring of additional training programs, as well as to actions for improving engagement and delivery.

Figure 4: Training and Skills Development Roadmap: Achieving Ambitious Upskilling and Reskilling Goals for CIP Professionals.

4. Conclusions and outlook for next report(s)

This second roadmap and value-added report builds on the foundation established in the previous edition, offering a deeper and broader analysis of the Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience (CIP/CIR) landscape. It provides a more detailed understanding of capability needs and gaps, informed by additional research and new stakeholder engagement activities, such as expert workshops.

A significant advancement in this report is the initial analysis of the CIP/CIR market, which extends beyond Europe to include insights from other global regions such as the USA and Asia-Pacific. This broader perspective enriches the recommendations and helps position the EU-CIP initiative within the international context.

Most importantly, this report introduces the structure and core content of the EU-CIP roadmap for research and innovation development. This roadmap outlines key measures and activities across research, technology development, training and upskilling, and the evolution of standards and regulations. The expanded scope and refined methodologies presented here are designed to support a wide range of stakeholders, from policymakers and industry leaders to researchers and practitioners.

To facilitate effective communication and uptake of the main recommendations, a concise version of the roadmap will be produced and disseminated separately to the wider community. Future reports will continue to build on these findings, incorporating updated analyses of capability needs, market developments, and stakeholder feedback. While the structure of the roadmap is expected to remain stable, its content and recommendations will evolve to reflect emerging trends and new insights.

By regularly updating and sharing these findings, the EU-CIP project aims to empower the CIP/CIR community with actionable intelligence, strategic foresight, and practical guidance—driving progress towards a more secure, resilient, and collaborative critical infrastructure landscape across Europe and beyond.

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6. Annex A: Status of CIP/CIR in 2024

In our contemporary and ever more interdependent and globalized world, Critical Infrastructure (CI) systems are the cornerstones of societies. They are complex, interrelated systems, networks, and services essential for everyday life, businesses, and social activities, and underwrite the security of societies and communities¹.

CI in its essence means defining the infrastructure, processes and systems that are crucial for the functioning of the wider social community. In the basic definition, the term “*Critical Infrastructure means an asset, system or part thereof located in Member States which is essential for the maintenance of vital societal functions, health, safety, security, economic or social well-being of people, and the disruption or destruction of which would have a significant impact in a Member State as a result of the failure to maintain those functions* (EU Directive, 2008²)”.

CI constitute the backbone of the functioning of our modern and interconnected societies. Major shock events of all types, from natural hazards to industrial accidents, terrorist or cyber-attacks, have demonstrated the vulnerabilities of these critical systems. Their destruction, disruption or interruption could lead to cascading effects across sectors and sometimes across national borders. Vulnerabilities of CI to this range of hazards and threats call for increased attention to CI security and resilience. Disaster risks, compounded by climate change, present a set of challenges for infrastructure resilience. In addition, the rise of hybrid threats and associated digital security risks calls for increased resilience of CI to digital security incidents³.

In the current landscape, CI systems are becoming more complex and interconnected, making them more vulnerable to cascading failures and disruptions. This makes it even more critical for these systems to be resilient and able to adapt and recover from disruptions. Furthermore, disruptions to CI systems are becoming more frequent and severe due to factors such as climate change, cyber threats, and pandemics. New security risks are emerging and the number of cyber-attacks against CI assets are increased.

The negative consequences to societies and communities arising from such disruptions include existing vulnerabilities being greatly exacerbated, new ones being created, and social inequalities becoming more entrenched⁴. CI systems need to be resilient in the current landscape due to the growing complexity and interconnectivity of these systems, as well as their criticality, the increasing frequency and severity of disruptions, and the high costs of disruptions. The resilience of CI refers to its ability to withstand, adapt to, and recover from disruptions, stresses, and shocks while maintaining its essential functions and services. Resilience is a critical aspect of CI, given the high likelihood of disruptions and the severe consequences of failures in these systems. Therefore, the importance of CI resilience is high on the agenda of contemporary sustainable development as the “keystone” of nationally led processes of building resilience and actions. In that regard, a resilient society is based

¹ Guidance notes on building Critical Infrastructure resilience in Europe and Central Asia, United Nations Development Programme. UNDP 2022

² European Council Directive 2008/114/EC on the identification and designation of European Critical Infrastructures and the assessment of the need to improve their protection. 2008.

<http://eurlex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2008:345:0075:0082:EN:PDF>

³ <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/76326acb-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/76326acb-en>

⁴ <https://www.undp.org/albania/publications/guidance-notes-building-critical-infrastructure-resilience-europe-and-central-asia>

on multidimensional principles that contribute to sustainable and resilient development. CI resilience can be understood as the ability of these systems to anticipate, withstand or absorb shocks and stresses, while adapting to new conditions that would result in a quick recovery and transformation as a way to better cope with chronic stresses and acute shocks in the future⁵.

6.1. Annex A.1: Critical Infrastructure Protection: A Complex Technological and Policy landscape

To ensure the resilience and the continuity of CIs, CI operators have deployed a host of different solutions, which range from security risk assessment and cyber security solutions to solutions that protect physical assets of CIs. The development of effective and innovative CIP solutions is vital, given the growing sophistication of the CIs and the emerging challenges and threats that are recently faced by operators. For instance, in an increasingly digitally interconnected world, CI operators need to deal with much more sophisticated cyber-security challenges than ever before. The latter include challenges (e.g., fake news and disinformation management) that were hardly considered in CIP solutions just a few years ago. Most importantly, CI owners and operators are nowadays conducting business in a highly unstructured, volatile, and highly unpredictable environment, where asymmetric threats and other previously rare events are becoming the norm. This has been very evident during the last couple of years, when several CI operators had to confront challenges like the COVID19 pandemic outbreak, various large scale supply chain disruptions following the pandemic, as well as the on-going Ukrainian war.

In this landscape, CI operators are forced to design and implement novel solutions that are not just reactive in nature, but rather are able to predict and anticipate potential disruptions and security threats. Recent technological advances yield the development of such solutions viable and more pragmatic than a few years ago. Nevertheless, the task of planning, designing, developing, deploying, and operating innovative solutions must take place within the scope of a complex landscape of multiple technological solutions, such as security risk assessment, adaptive threat hunting, anomaly detection, biometric authentication, blockchain technology, cyber-physical threat intelligence, data loss prevention, digital twins, disinformation management, end-point protection, image analysis, impact assessment, machine learning, modelling of cascading effects, and pentesting solutions.

There are also emerging technological solutions (e.g., generative AI⁶) that present both opportunities and threats to strengthening critical infrastructure protection (CIP).

- A sea of different standards, such as ISO/TC 292, the ISO 27001 series, the ISO 28000 series, and the ISO 22000 facilities of standards, which cover a many different aspects of CI protection aspects.
- A considerable number of regulations and directives, such as the NIS directive, the GDPR regulation, the AI Act of the council of Europe, the cybersecurity Act, and many more.
- A multi-stakeholder environment, including not only CI owners and operators, but also technology vendors, researchers, security experts, security integrators, regulatory experts and

⁵ <https://www.undp.org/albania/publications/guidance-notes-building-critical-infrastructure-resilience-europe-and-central-asia>

⁶ M. Gupta, C. Akiri, K. Aryal, E. Parker and L. Praharaj, "From ChatGPT to ThreatGPT: Impact of Generative AI in Cybersecurity and Privacy," in IEEE Access, vol. 11, pp. 80218-80245, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3300381.

policy makers, which view the development and deployment of innovative solutions from their own unique perspective.

- A host of opportunities for combining diverse technologies into more complex, integrated, and sophisticated solutions. For instance, these opportunities can be boosted by an amalgamation of advanced technologies such as big data, IoT, IIoT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), cloud computing, digital twins, edge computing, advanced analytics, robotics, cognitive computing, etc.

Within this complex landscape, stakeholders need orientation regarding available solutions, gaps in current knowledge, limitations of the state of the art and the state of practice, as well as roadmaps for the development and deployment of innovative CIP solutions.

The landscape of resilience research in the EU, the context of which directly affects endeavours like the EU-CIP project, confronts several pressing issues, each bearing considerable consequences. First and foremost, among these challenges is the persistent problem of **stakeholder engagement**. While there is an overarching consensus on the necessity of involving all relevant stakeholders and fostering meaningful dialogue, the practical implementation often falls short due to constraints like time limitations, resource scarcity, and at times, a lack of willingness to engage fully. This paradox highlights the urgency of not just advocating for inclusivity but also of dedicating the necessary resources and commitment to ensure that the voices and expertise of all stakeholders are genuinely heard and valued. In the absence of such engagement, the development and execution of comprehensive resilience strategies will remain compromised, as the richness of diverse perspectives and experiences remains untapped.

A second critical challenge lies in the **realm of data and information**. Stakeholders widely acknowledge the imperative of consolidating and aligning data and information sources to inform resilience efforts effectively. However, this seemingly straightforward objective often encounters substantial roadblocks. High-quality, comprehensive, and up-to-date data is not consistently provided, undermining the foundations of sound decision-making and the development of robust resilience initiatives. The dearth of reliable information can lead to blind spots and suboptimal resource allocation, ultimately impeding progress in building resilient systems.

Lastly, there exists a distinct need for representative, qualified **alignment, consultation, and policy development**. The ideal of shaping EU policies through two-way consultations resonates across the stakeholder spectrum. However, the execution of this vision frequently falls short of expectations. Stakeholders may not participate in consultations with the vigour required, leading to responses that lack true representativeness. Moreover, key stakeholders are sometimes conspicuously absent from these vital dialogues, resulting in policy outcomes that may not adequately address the concerns and needs of all parties involved. The quality and relevance of stakeholders' contributions to policy formation also demand more scrutiny and enhancement.

These three core issues collectively underscore the multifaceted and intricate nature of resilience research within the European context. Overcoming these challenges necessitates a concerted, sustained effort, with a commitment to genuine engagement, data quality enhancement, and the cultivation of policies that are not only informed but also endorsed by the diverse array of stakeholders involved.

7. Annex B: Capability Needs in CIP/CIR

In this Annex the activities and applied assessment methods to identify the capability gaps of CIP/CIR are briefly described.

7.1. Annex B.1: The EU-CIP Analysis Activities

One of the main objectives of EU-CIP is to enhance Europe's analytical capability regarding research outcomes, technologies, and policies to foster data-driven evidence-based policy and innovation development. The activities that will lead to the accomplishment of this objective are conveniently called EU-CIP-ANALYSIS activities. The EU-CIP-ANALYSIS activities will be implemented over a period of three years following the start of the project in October 2022. Some of the findings of the EU-CIP-ANALYSIS, notably those from a state of the art analysis and consultation with CIP stakeholders within the EU-CIP consortium and the ECSCI (European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures) cluster i.e., a cluster comprising more than 30 of the most prominent European projects on security and CIs protection and protection have been gathered.

The point of origination is based on a careful analysis of information and insights from the internal consultation survey. This survey has highlighted gaps in the existing solutions essential for Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR). These gaps form the foundation for this task, as the survey has helped identify a comprehensive list of capability needs and areas for improvement. EU-CIP consortium members have identified some CIP capabilities that are not adequately supported and covered by existing solutions. Furthermore, The EU-CIP consortium members have also identified a list of preliminary Capability Gaps (CG), which are partly linked to the above needs.

7.2. Annex B.2: Capability Needs Assessment

The EU-CIP consortium members have identified the following CIP capabilities that are not adequately supported and covered by state-of-the-art solutions:

- **C1 - Enhanced adaptability:** There is a need to enhance adaptability to new threats, as the novel and sometimes asymmetric threats against CIs happen with higher frequency than ever before. The capability need C1 - Enhanced Adaptability, is a fundamental requirement within the CIP domain. This need underscores the imperative to improve the ability of organizations and systems responsible for safeguarding critical infrastructure to adapt effectively to the ever-evolving landscape of threats and challenges. Enhanced adaptability refers to the capacity of CI stakeholders to respond and adjust rapidly to emerging threats, whether they are novel, asymmetric, or otherwise unforeseen. It acknowledges the dynamic nature of threats facing CIs, which can include cyberattacks, physical attacks, natural disasters, or a combination of these factors. Adaptability is vital because threats are evolving, and the ability to stay ahead of them is crucial for the security and resilience of critical infrastructure. The capability need for enhanced adaptability is crucial in the context of CIP. It acknowledges the dynamic and evolving nature of threats and the necessity for organizations responsible for safeguarding critical infrastructure to be agile, responsive, and proactive in their approach to security and

resilience. This adaptability is essential for staying ahead of emerging threats and effectively mitigating their impact on critical infrastructure assets and systems.

Enhancing adaptability in CIP presents several challenges. These include the need for robust intelligence and threat monitoring, the capacity to rapidly implement changes in response to emerging threats, and the necessity of securing budgets and resources to support ongoing adaptability efforts, which by definition is a continuous process.

- **C2 - Reduced Response Times:** EU-CIP experts identified a need for increasing the speed of response as a means of coping with highly volatile environments and minimize the costs of potential damage. This need underscores the importance of minimizing the time it takes for organizations responsible for safeguarding CI to respond to threats, incidents, or emergencies. Reduced response times refer to the ability to quickly detect, assess, and respond to threats, incidents, or disruptions within the CI environment. It acknowledges that in highly volatile and dynamic environments, delays in response can lead to increased costs, damage, and potential cascading effects that impact not only the infrastructure itself but also broader societal and economic stability. The reference to highly volatile environments implies that the landscape in which CIs operate is subject to rapid changes, including emerging threats, cyberattacks, natural disasters, and geopolitical factors. These volatile conditions demand swift and agile responses to mitigate potential consequences. One of the primary motivations for reducing response times is to minimize the costs associated with security incidents or disruptions. Rapid response can help prevent or limit the extent of damage, reduce downtime, and avoid costly recovery efforts. It can also prevent the escalation of incidents into larger, more widespread crises. In an increasingly dynamic and volatile environment, reducing response times is essential for maintaining the security, resilience, and reliability of critical infrastructure assets and systems.

Reducing response times in CIP presents several challenges, including the need for robust monitoring and early warning systems, effective communication and coordination among multiple stakeholders, and the development of clear response protocols and procedures.

- **C3 - Increased Transparency:** In an era where complex threats are handled by sophisticated technologies, there is a need for improving the transparency of the solution for stakeholders. This need emphasizes the importance of enhancing the transparency of security solutions and practices related to CI. Increased transparency refers to the practice of making security measures, technologies, and processes more visible and understandable to stakeholders involved in CIP. In an era characterized by complex and evolving threats, transparency is essential for building trust, facilitating collaboration, and ensuring accountability among stakeholders, while promoting a better understanding of the security measures in place to address complex and evolving threats. By enhancing transparency, organizations can work together more effectively to safeguard CI assets and systems. Security solutions in the modern CIP landscape often rely on sophisticated technologies such as AI, IoT, and advanced encryption methods. While these technologies are effective, they can be complex and may not be easily understood by all stakeholders. Increased transparency aims to bridge this knowledge gap by providing stakeholders with a clear view of how these technologies work and how they contribute to security.

Increasing transparency in CIP faces challenges such as the need to balance transparency with security, protecting sensitive information, and the potential for information overload. Striking the right balance between transparency and security is essential.

- **C4 - Improved Detection Capabilities:** Improved detection over the current state-of-the-art based on solutions that: (i) address novel threats like hybrid threats which combine cyber security and physical security aspects and (ii) provide improved analytics capabilities for detection and response tools that account for the rapid shifting in the IoT and 5G spaces, while offering improved informed decision making. This need underscores the necessity of enhancing the ability to detect threats, particularly within the context of novel and rapidly evolving challenges. Improved detection capabilities refer to the ability to identify and recognize threats, vulnerabilities, or anomalies with greater accuracy, speed, and efficiency than current state-of-the-art solutions. Detection is a fundamental component of CIP, as it enables early response and mitigation of potential risks to CI. By enhancing detection accuracy, speed, and adaptability, organizations can better protect CI assets and systems and make more informed decisions in rapidly changing threat environments.

Improving detection capabilities in CIP is challenging due to the rapidly changing threat landscape, the complexity of hybrid threats, and the need for real-time decision-making.

- **C5 - Improved risk and impact assessment capabilities** to address novel integrated, hybrid, and asymmetric threats against a broad range of cyber and physical assets. This need emphasizes the importance of enhancing the ability to assess risks and evaluate the potential impacts of emerging and diverse threats on both cyber and physical assets. Improved risk and impact assessment capabilities refer to the capacity to thoroughly evaluate and understand the risks associated with CI and to assess the potential consequences of various threats. This capability is essential for identifying vulnerabilities, developing mitigation strategies, and making informed decisions to protect both cyber and physical assets. By enhancing these capabilities, organizations can better understand and prepare for the risks associated with novel, integrated, hybrid, and asymmetric threats, ultimately leading to the more effective protection and resilience of CI assets and systems.

Improved risk and impact assessment capabilities face challenges such as the complexity of hybrid threats, the need for comprehensive data collection and analysis, and the requirement for cross-disciplinary expertise. Additionally, assessing the interdependencies between different CI components can be challenging.

- **C6 - Better integration of Telco Security tools with Information Security Management tools.** This integration should strive to avoid existing silos and fragmentation in security systems and capabilities. This need emphasizes the importance of seamlessly integrating telecommunications (telco) security tools with information security management tools to eliminate existing silos and fragmentation in security systems and capabilities. Better integration of telco security tools with information security management tools refers to the process of harmonizing and unifying security measures and technologies across telecommunications infrastructure and information systems. This integration is crucial because it addresses the fragmentation and isolated security solutions that may exist within CI organizations. By harmonizing security efforts across telecommunications and information systems, organizations can achieve a more efficient, coordinated, and holistic approach to safeguarding CI assets and systems, reducing the risk of cyber threats and vulnerabilities.

The challenges associated with this capability need include the technical complexity of integrating diverse security tools, the need for standardized protocols and interfaces, and the necessity of aligning security policies and practices across telecommunications and information systems.

- **C7 – Solutions addressing cascading effects between different entities and states.** Such solutions must help prevent disruptions on supply chain services, thus helping to ensure the continuity of business operations across different value chains. This need highlights the significance of developing solutions that can mitigate and manage the cascading effects of disruptions within the interconnected CI landscape, especially in the context of supply chain services. Solutions addressing cascading effects refer to measures and strategies aimed at understanding, preventing, and mitigating the ripple effects of disruptions within the CI ecosystem. These disruptions can originate from various sources, such as cyberattacks, natural disasters, or other forms of threats. Cascading effects involve the spread of disruptions across different entities, sectors, and even international borders. CI systems are highly interconnected, with dependencies on each other for their operations. For example, a disruption in one sector, like energy or transportation, can have far-reaching consequences, affecting multiple value chains, businesses, and even countries. The significance of addressing cascading effects lies in maintaining the continuity of business operations and societal functions. By proactively identifying, mitigating against, and managing the consequences of disruptions that propagate across interconnected CI systems, organizations can enhance resilience, minimize economic and societal impacts, and ensure the continuity of business operations and essential services.

Addressing cascading effects presents challenges such as identifying complex interdependencies, developing comprehensive risk assessment methodologies, ensuring cross-sector and international collaboration, and allocating resources for preparedness and mitigation efforts.

- **C8 - Transformation of proactive and adaptive protection tools and methods to incorporate real-time functionalities.** Such functionalities will boost the protection and resilience of CI through the improved collection and analysis of real-time data in light of the ever evolving and dynamically changing threat landscape. This need underscores the necessity of adapting protection strategies and tools to operate in real-time, thereby enhancing the security and resilience of CI in the face of evolving and dynamic threats. The transformation of proactive and adaptive protection tools and methods to incorporate real-time functionalities refers to the integration of real-time data collection, analysis, and response mechanisms into CI security strategies. This transformation aims to enable rapid responses to emerging threats, vulnerabilities, and incidents within the continuously changing threat landscape. By enabling rapid threat detection, immediate response, and enhanced situational awareness, organizations can better protect CI assets and systems in the face of an ever evolving and dynamic threat landscape, ultimately enhancing their resilience and security posture.

Implementing real-time functionalities in CIP presents challenges such as the need for advanced monitoring systems, the integration of data from diverse sources, and the development of automated response mechanisms. There are also issues related to data privacy and ensuring the accuracy and reliability of real-time data.

- **C9 – Better exploitation of information from critical sensors towards augmented situation awareness.** Input from critical sensors (e.g., cameras, human presence, luminosity, weather/environmental parameters) must be better integrated and exploited within CIP systems towards improving situation awareness (e.g., about security personnel positions and the state of CI assets). The latter must be combined with proper revisions to security and emergency management processes. This need emphasizes the importance of harnessing data from critical sensors to enhance situational awareness and improve the security and emergency management processes. Better exploitation of

information from critical sensors involves the effective collection, integration, and utilization of data gathered by sensors deployed in CI environments. These sensors provide valuable insights into the status and conditions of critical assets, as well as potential security threats. By harnessing the wealth of data generated by these sensors and integrating it into security and emergency management processes, organizations can enhance their situational awareness, respond more effectively to security threats, and ultimately strengthen the protection and resilience of CI assets and systems.

Challenges associated with this capability need include managing the sheer volume of data generated by sensors, ensuring data privacy and security, and integrating sensor data with existing CIP systems and processes. Additionally, there may be issues related to interoperability between sensors from different vendors and standardizing data formats.

- **C10 – Risk prediction and anticipation**, leading to the earlier detection of threats and subsequently enhancing resilience, monitoring, patrolling, decision support, and event management applications. This need emphasizes the importance of implementing predictive and anticipatory capabilities to enhance the resilience of CI by detecting threats at an earlier stage and enabling more effective decision-making and response. Risk prediction and anticipation involve the use of advanced data analytics, modelling, and threat intelligence to foresee potential threats and vulnerabilities that could impact CI. The significance lies in the ability to proactively detect emerging threats and prepare for them in advance. The core objective of this capability need is the early detection of threats, whether they are cyber threats, physical security risks, natural disasters, or other forms of potential disruptions. Early detection allows for timely responses, minimizing the impact of these threats. By identifying and anticipating risks in advance, CI organizations can take proactive measures to enhance their resilience. This includes strengthening defences, developing contingency plans, and allocating resources strategically. By proactively identifying and preparing for potential threats and vulnerabilities, organizations can enhance the resilience of CI, minimize the impact of disruptions, and make more informed decisions, ultimately ensuring the continuity of business operations and essential services.

Challenges associated with this capability need include the complexity of predicting multifaceted threats, the importance of accurate and timely data, and the requirement for sophisticated analytics and modelling capabilities. Additionally, organizations must ensure that predictive models and algorithms are continuously updated to remain effective.

- **C11 – Training, Reskilling and Upskilling**. There is a need for developing relevant skills and competences in collaboration with the research and academic communities. Prominent examples of the required skills development include cybersecurity and cyber-resilience trainings. This need underscores the importance of continuously developing and enhancing the skills and competencies of personnel involved in CIP. Prominent areas of focus for skills development include cybersecurity and cyber-resilience training. Training, reskilling, and upskilling refer to the processes of providing education, training, and professional development opportunities to individuals working in the field of CIP. The significance of this capability need lies in ensuring that personnel possess the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively protect CI against evolving threats.

Challenges associated with this capability need include the requirement for ongoing training to keep up with evolving threats, the recruitment and retention of skilled personnel, and the development of comprehensive and up-to-date training programs.

Furthermore, additional Capability Needs have been provided from a deeper analysis of the current landscape:

- **C12 - Supply Chain Security:** Strengthening supply chain security is vital to prevent vulnerabilities in the production and delivery of CI components. Supply Chain Security is a critical capability need within the realm of CIP, given the interconnected nature of modern supply chains and the potential for significant economic and security implications in case of disruptions. It pertains to the safeguarding of all processes, resources, and systems involved in the production, transportation, and distribution of goods and services. Supply chain security encompasses the protection of all stages of the supply chain, from raw material suppliers to manufacturers, logistics providers, distributors, and ultimately the end consumers. It involves ensuring the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of goods and information as they move through the supply chain. Supply chains are the lifeblood of modern economies, and any disruption can have severe consequences. Attacks or disruptions in the supply chain can lead to delays, increased costs, and even critical shortages. The consequences can range from financial losses to threats to public safety, particularly in industries like healthcare, energy, and transportation. The supply chain is vulnerable to various threats, including cyberattacks on logistics systems, theft of goods, counterfeit products, and natural disasters. In recent years, cyber threats have become particularly concerning, as they can target CI assets within the supply chain. Protecting the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of goods and information throughout the supply chain is essential to ensure the resilience and security of CI.

Several challenges make supply chain security complex. These include the globalization of supply chains, the use of numerous suppliers and subcontractors, reliance on digital technologies, and the dynamic nature of threats. Additionally, supply chain security requires collaboration among multiple stakeholders, making coordination and information sharing essential.

- **C13 - Public-Private Collaboration Frameworks:** Public-Private Collaboration Frameworks refer to the structured mechanisms and partnerships established between governmental or public-sector entities and private-sector organizations to enhance CIP. The significance of this capability need lies in the recognition that CI systems often involve a mix of public and private ownership and operation, necessitating coordinated efforts to safeguard them effectively. Establishing effective collaboration mechanisms between public and private sectors is crucial for sharing threat intelligence and responding to incidents. Public-private collaboration allows for a more coordinated and effective response to security incidents. Shared threat intelligence, situational awareness, and resources enable stakeholders to act promptly and decisively, resulting in a more comprehensive view of the threat landscape. This shared information empowers stakeholders to make informed decisions. The establishment of effective mechanisms for cooperation ensures that both sectors work together to protect CI, respond to threats, and maintain essential services. The implications of this capability need encompass improved threat response, information sharing, resource allocation, innovation, policy development, and overall resilience enhancement within the CI landscape.

Despite its importance and benefits, public-private collaboration in CIP faces challenges. Private sector organizations may be hesitant to share sensitive information with government agencies due to concerns about data privacy, proprietary information, and regulatory compliance. Building trust and effective coordination mechanisms between public and private entities can therefore be difficult.

- **C14 - Cross-Border Coordination:** This involves enhanced coordination and information sharing with international partners, especially in cases where threats and vulnerabilities cross

national borders. Cooperation between neighbouring countries is vital for addressing transnational security challenges. Cross-border coordination in the context of CIP involves the establishment of collaborative mechanisms and partnerships between countries or international entities to enhance the security and resilience of CI that spans national borders. This capability need is of paramount significance due to the interconnected nature of modern CI systems and the globalized threat landscape. Many CI systems, such as energy grids, transportation networks, and communication systems, extend beyond national borders. Threats to these systems can, therefore, transcend boundaries. Effective cross-border coordination is essential for a unified response. Collaboration between neighbouring countries and international partners allows for the pooling of resources, expertise, and intelligence. This shared approach enhances the collective ability to detect, prevent, and respond to security incidents. In times of crisis, cooperation with neighbouring countries and international partners ensures mutual support. Assistance in responding to and recovering from large-scale incidents can be crucial for minimizing the impact on CI. Cross-border coordination enhances the ability to respond swiftly and effectively to transnational security threats. Shared intelligence and coordinated efforts allow for a more comprehensive response. Collaborative information sharing across borders provides a broader view of the threat landscape. This shared knowledge empowers stakeholders to make well-informed decisions and adapt their security strategies. It emphasizes the importance of countries and international entities working together to protect shared critical assets, respond to threats, and ensure the resilience of interconnected systems. While there are challenges to overcome, the benefits of cross-border coordination in CIP are substantial and contribute to a safer and more secure global CI landscape.

Sharing sensitive information across borders raises concerns about data privacy and security. Countries must establish secure communication channels and agreements to protect shared data. Differences in legal frameworks and regulatory requirements across borders can, however, complicate information sharing and coordination efforts, making harmonizing these aspects is a challenge.

- **C15 - Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery (BCDR):** Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery refers to the strategic planning and implementation of measures to ensure the continuous operation and rapid restoration of CI systems in the event of disruptions, including cyberattacks, physical threats, natural disasters, or other incidents. This capability need is of paramount importance because it ensures the resilience and availability of CI services, which are vital for societies and economies. Maintaining the continuous operation of CI services is essential for public safety, national security, and economic stability. BCDR plans ensure that essential services are minimally impacted upon and/or are quickly restored. BCDR planning includes proactive measures to prepare for potential disasters and disruptions, which reduces the severity of the impact and enables more efficient recovery. BCDR plans enable rapid recovery and restoration of CI services, minimizing downtime and reducing the impact of disruptions on society and the economy. BCDR planning ensures that essential services can continue to operate or be rapidly restored in the face of disruptions. It encompasses disaster preparedness, cybersecurity resilience, resource allocation, and public trust-building. While challenges exist, effective BCDR planning is indispensable for the security, resilience, and continuity of CI systems.

BCDR planning for CI can be complex due to the interconnected nature of systems, diverse threats, and the need for comprehensive strategies.

- **C16 - Resilience Metrics and Reporting:** Resilience Metrics and Reporting refer to the establishment of standardized metrics and reporting mechanisms that assess the resilience of CI and communicate its status to various stakeholders, including regulatory bodies, government agencies, industry partners, and the public. This capability need is significant as it provides a structured approach to measuring and reporting on the resilience of CI, allowing for informed decision-making and transparency. Resilience metrics enable the systematic assessment of CIs' ability to withstand and recover from disruptions, including cyberattacks, physical threats, and natural disasters. Resilience metrics provide a quantitative view of a CI's ability to withstand and recover from disruptions. This allows for comparisons over time and across different CI components. Standardized metrics provide decision-makers with quantifiable data to make informed choices regarding resource allocation, risk mitigation, and investment in CI protection.

Collecting relevant data for resilience metrics can be challenging, as it may require cooperation from various stakeholders and access to sensitive information. CI systems are highly interconnected, making it difficult to isolate the impact of a disruption on a single component. Metrics must account for this complexity. Developing standardized metrics that are applicable across diverse CI sectors and organizations can be also complex due to sector-specific differences.

Addressing these capability needs (C1 to C16) is essential for enhancing the protection and resilience of CI. Input from various stakeholders, including government, industry, technology providers, and the public, is crucial to developing effective solutions. These capabilities should be seen as an integrated approach to safeguarding CI in an increasingly complex threat landscape.

7.2.1. Annex B.2.1: Implications

A more comprehensive analysis of the implications of the identified capability needs for the protection and resilience of CI is fundamental. The implications of the identified capability needs are multifaceted and profoundly influential in bolstering the protection and resilience of CI.

- Enhanced adaptability (C1) recognises the imperative of swiftly adapting to novel, asymmetric threats that increasingly target CI. In an era of evolving cyber and physical risks, this adaptability ensures that security measures remain relevant and effective.
- Reduced response times (C2) play a pivotal role in mitigating the potentially catastrophic consequences of volatile environments. By accelerating the response to threats, the ability to minimize damage and ensure the continuity of vital services is significantly enhanced.
- Increased transparency (C3) fosters trust among stakeholders, providing them with insights into the efficacy of security measures. Transparency is a cornerstone of effective collaboration between the public and private sectors, as well as among various infrastructure operators, all of which are essential for comprehensive protection.
- Improved detection capabilities (C4) are paramount in identifying complex threats in a landscape where cyber and physical security converge. These capabilities enable early threat identification, enhancing the ability to respond effectively and to mitigate potential harm.
- Better risk and impact assessment (C5) are integral in prioritizing security efforts and allocating resources judiciously. Informed decision-making relies on a deep understanding of potential risks, making risk assessment an indispensable tool.

- Better integration of Telco security tools (C6) addresses the fragmentation and silos that can create vulnerabilities within security systems. This integration paves the way for seamless coordination and information sharing among various components of CI.
- Solutions addressing cascading effects (C7) are pivotal in preventing disruptions in supply chain services, ensuring the uninterrupted flow of essential goods and services. In an interconnected world, where the failure of one entity can trigger a chain reaction, these solutions are crucial.
- Transformation toward real-time functionalities (C8) acknowledges the importance of dynamic threat landscapes. These functionalities enable real-time data collection and analysis, allowing for proactive responses to emerging threats.
- Better exploitation of critical sensors (C9) extends situational awareness by incorporating data from sensors like cameras and environmental parameters. This insight enhances security personnel's ability to monitor and respond to threats effectively.
- Risk prediction and anticipation (C10) employ advanced algorithms and analytics to foresee potential threats, leading to earlier detection, improved resilience, and informed decision-making across various applications, from monitoring to event management.
- Training, reskilling, and upskilling (C11) are fundamental to building a skilled workforce equipped to handle evolving threats. Collaboration with academic and research communities is essential for developing the required skills, especially in cybersecurity and cyber-resilience.
- In addition to the identified needs, supply chain security (C12) is imperative, ensuring the integrity of components and services critical to infrastructure.
- Public-private collaboration frameworks (C13) provide the mechanism for information sharing and coordinated responses, enabling stakeholders to collectively address emerging threats effectively.
- The implication of capability need C14 dealing with Cross-Border Coordination is profound within the context of safeguarding CI as it signifies the recognition that CI often extends across national borders and that threats, whether they be cyberattacks, physical disruptions, or natural disasters, do not adhere to geopolitical boundaries. By addressing this need, organizations and governments acknowledge the necessity of working collaboratively with neighbouring countries and international partners to establish unified strategies for threat detection, incident response, and recovery efforts. This implies improved information sharing, resource coordination, and the harmonization of policies and regulations across borders. The result is a more robust and resilient CI landscape that can collectively respond to and recover from transnational security challenges, ultimately enhancing the security and continuity of essential services on a global scale.
- Capability need C15, Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery (BCDR), carries significant implications for the security and resilience of CI. It underscores the importance of systematically planning for disruptions, whether they are caused by cyberattacks, physical incidents, or natural disasters. The implication is that organizations responsible for CI must prioritize the development of robust BCDR plans to ensure the uninterrupted operation of essential services. This means proactive measures to prepare for contingencies, cybersecurity integration, resource allocation, and regular testing and training. The implication of C15 is twofold: first, it leads to the rapid recovery of services in the face of disruptions, minimizing downtime and reducing their impact on society and the economy; second, it fosters a culture of preparedness, resilience, and accountability, instilling confidence in the public and stakeholders that CI will continue to function even during challenging times.

- Capability Need C16, Resilience Metrics and Reporting, has far-reaching implications for the CIP landscape. It emphasizes the need for standardized and quantifiable measures to assess and communicate the resilience of CI systems. The implication is the establishment of a structured approach to evaluating and improving resilience, providing decision-makers with data-driven insights into vulnerabilities and strengths. This capability need ensures that organizations responsible for CIP can make informed decisions, allocate resources effectively, and adhere to regulatory requirements. It fosters transparency and accountability, building trust among stakeholders and the public. Ultimately, by addressing C16, organizations enhance their ability to withstand and recover from disruptions, contributing to the overall security and resilience of CI systems.

In conclusion, the implications of these capability needs are far-reaching, encompassing the realms of adaptability, transparency, detection, risk assessment, integration, resilience, and expertise development. Addressing these needs collectively and collaboratively is essential for the robust protection and resilience of CI in an increasingly interconnected and rapidly evolving threat landscape.

8. Annex C: Capability gaps in CIP/CIR

In order to enhance CIP/CIR, the first and important step is to identify the gaps and needs of these infrastructures. Hence, one of the pillars of EU-CIP aims to analyse the current CIP/CIR landscape.

8.1. Annex C.1: Capability gaps analysis

EU-CIP has identified a list of preliminary Capability Gaps (CG), which are partly linked to the above listed capability needs. The Capability Gaps Analysis sheds light on critical vulnerabilities within the realm of critical infrastructure protection (CIP). These gaps represent shortcomings in the current state of preparedness and underscore the pressing need for comprehensive solutions:

- **CG1 - Poor Automation:** There is currently poor automation when it comes to achieving fast detection, protection, and recovery from cyber-attacks. Specifically, there is a gap in closing the cybersecurity automation loop to automatically verify, diagnose, rectify, monitor, measure, and improve security controls. This gap is very evident when it comes to supporting heterogeneous technology and configurations in a systematic and justifiable manner. Rapidly developing technologies like Artificial Intelligence can greatly boost automation in processes like threat detection, attack anticipation, and fast enforcement of security policies, yet their use must adhere to the mandates of emerging regulations (e.g., the European AI Act). The poor automation of CIP processes presents significant challenges in the current threat landscape. The gap primarily stems from the inability to effectively automate key aspects of cybersecurity operations, including threat detection, response, and recovery. This deficiency is particularly pronounced when dealing with diverse and heterogeneous technology environments, which are common in CI sectors. The lack of automation slows down the response to cyberattacks, making it difficult to detect and mitigate threats quickly. This delay can result in prolonged disruptions and increased vulnerabilities. The poor automation of cybersecurity processes poses a significant challenge in responding effectively to cyber threats. In today's rapidly evolving threat landscape, manual responses are often too slow and inadequate. Automating threat detection, response, and recovery processes is essential to keep up with the speed and complexity of cyberattacks. However, it's crucial to ensure that automation aligns with emerging regulations like the European AI Act, emphasizing responsible and ethical AI usage.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Slow Detection and Response:** Poor automation results in slow detection and response times to cyber threats. This delay provides attackers with a greater window of opportunity to exploit vulnerabilities, increasing the risk of successful attacks.
- **Inconsistencies in Security Controls:** Without automation, security controls and response procedures may be applied inconsistently across CI components. This inconsistency can create weak points that attackers can exploit.
- **Resource Intensiveness:** Manual intervention in security processes consumes valuable human resources. This limits the ability to monitor and protect CI systems around the clock, leaving them vulnerable during off-hours.
- **Human Error:** Relying on manual processes increases the likelihood of human error, such as misconfigurations or missed alerts. These errors can create vulnerabilities that attackers can leverage.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- Increased Vulnerability to Attacks: Without addressing the automation gap, CI remains highly vulnerable to cyberattacks, including those with potentially devastating consequences such as disruptions to essential services or data breaches.
 - Extended Downtime: Slow detection and response times can lead to extended downtime during and after cyber incidents. This downtime disrupts critical services, affecting public safety and economic stability.
 - Resource Depletion: Manual intervention in cybersecurity processes strains human resources and can lead to resource depletion. Organizations may struggle to allocate sufficient staff to manage security, leaving CI exposed.
 - Ineffective Compliance: Failure to address the gap makes it challenging to comply with emerging regulations, potentially resulting in legal and regulatory penalties and reputational damage.
 - Financial Impact: Cyberattacks and disruptions to CI often entail significant financial costs, including incident recovery expenses, legal fees, and potential fines.
 - Loss of Public Trust: Prolonged downtime and frequent incidents erode public trust in CI operators' ability to provide reliable and secure services. This loss of trust can have long-term consequences.
 - National Security Risks: Vulnerabilities in CI can pose national security risks, as adversaries may exploit these weaknesses for geopolitical advantage or to disrupt a country's stability.
- **CG2 – Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness:** CI operators currently do not have strong control over interconnected assets and their dependencies. This makes it difficult to implement a holistic CIP approach that considers the dependencies of the various assets, as well as related cascading effects. To boost the interconnectedness of diverse assets and of their security policies, there is a need for novel security knowledge modelling approaches, as well as for interconnection and interoperability across diverse security systems. This capability gap underscores a critical challenge in the realm of CIP. It highlights the difficulty faced by CI operators in maintaining robust control over interconnected assets and understanding their complex dependencies. This lack of control inhibits the implementation of a comprehensive CIP strategy, as well as the consideration of cascading effects that can result from disruptions to various assets. To address this gap effectively, novel approaches to security knowledge modelling, interconnection, and interoperability are necessary. The lack of robust control over interconnected assets and their dependencies is a critical vulnerability in safeguarding CI. When interdependencies are not adequately managed, the risk of cascading failures and widespread disruptions increases significantly. To address this gap, innovative approaches such as security knowledge modelling and interoperability solutions are vital. Establishing interoperability across diverse security systems is essential for comprehensive protection.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- Undisclosed Dependencies: Without proper control and understanding of interconnected assets and their dependencies, CI operators may not be aware of all the components that rely on each other. This lack of visibility creates blind spots, making it easier for attackers to exploit vulnerabilities in the system.

- **Ineffective Risk Assessment:** Inadequate control over interconnectedness makes it challenging to conduct thorough risk assessments. CI operators may struggle to identify and prioritize potential threats and vulnerabilities accurately.
- **Limited Resilience Planning:** The absence of strong control impedes the development of comprehensive resilience plans. Without considering interdependencies, CI operators may not have effective strategies in place to mitigate the cascading effects of disruptions.
- **Inefficient Resource Allocation:** CI operators may allocate resources inefficiently, focusing on isolated components while neglecting critical dependencies. This misallocation can result in inadequate protection for interconnected assets.
- **Inconsistent Security Policies:** Inconsistent security policies across interconnected assets creates vulnerabilities. Attackers can exploit weak links in the CI by targeting assets with less stringent security measures.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Increased Vulnerability:** Neglecting to address the gap in controlling interconnectedness raises the overall vulnerability of CI. Attackers can exploit undisclosed dependencies and weak links, potentially causing widespread disruptions.
 - **Cascading Effects:** Without proper control, disruptions in one area of the CI can cascade through interconnected assets, resulting in more extensive and severe failures. This can lead to extended downtime and greater impact.
 - **Ineffective Incident Response:** Inadequate control hampers the ability to respond effectively to incidents. CI operators may struggle to identify the root causes of disruptions, leading to delayed or ineffective response efforts.
 - **Resource Inefficiency:** Resource allocation may be inefficient, with investments in less critical areas and the neglect of crucial dependencies. This inefficiency can result in wasted resources and an inadequate security posture.
 - **Regulatory Non-Compliance:** CI operators may face challenges in complying with regulations that require a comprehensive understanding and management of dependencies. Non-compliance can lead to legal and financial consequences.
 - **Public Trust Erosion:** The inability to prevent and mitigate disruptions due to poor control over interconnectedness can erode public trust in CI operators' ability to provide reliable and secure services.
 - **Incomplete Risk Mitigation:** Inadequate risk assessment and planning can lead to incomplete risk mitigation strategies, leaving critical assets exposed to avoidable threats.
- **CG3 – Poor Alignment of Resilience Indicators:** Currently, CI operators deal with a host of resilience indicators which are not aligned and, in a number of cases, diverse and non-compatible. This hinders the implementation of a structured CIR approach, while being a setback to interoperability across different interconnected CIs that support prominent value chains of our societies and economies. The capability gap identified in CG3 highlights a significant challenge in the CIP landscape. This gap pertains to the lack of consistency and alignment in the indicators and metrics used to assess the resilience of CI. Resilience indicators are essential for measuring and monitoring the ability of CI systems to withstand and recover from disruptions, be they cyber incidents, physical threats, or natural disasters. Poor alignment in this context results in a lack of standardized metrics and reporting mechanisms, making it difficult for stakeholders to assess and communicate CI resilience effectively. The poor alignment of resilience indicators across CI sectors complicates the implementation of a structured critical incident response approach. Inconsistent and non-compatible indicators hinder effective collaboration and coordinated responses to incidents.

The interconnected nature of CIs demands a common language for resilience indicators. Standardization and alignment are essential to enable seamless cooperation across various sectors.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Ineffective Risk Assessment:** Poorly aligned resilience indicators hinder the ability to assess and understand the vulnerabilities and risks faced by CI components accurately. Without standardized metrics, organizations may overlook critical vulnerabilities in their systems.
- **Inconsistent Preparedness:** The absence of standardized indicators makes it difficult for CI operators to consistently prepare for potential disruptions. As a result, they may not be adequately equipped to respond to diverse threats, leaving vulnerabilities unaddressed.
- **Limited Monitoring and Response:** Poor alignment affects the monitoring and response capabilities of CI operators. Without a uniform set of indicators, it is challenging to detect anomalies and respond promptly to security incidents or disruptions.
- **Resource Allocation Challenges:** The lack of standardized metrics complicates resource allocation for resilience improvement efforts. Organizations may misallocate resources, either overinvesting in less critical areas or neglecting essential vulnerabilities.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Increased Vulnerability:** Neglecting the alignment of resilience indicators heightens the vulnerability of CI to a wide range of threats, including cyberattacks, physical disruptions, and natural disasters.
 - **Inefficient Resource Use:** Organizations may inefficiently allocate resources to resilience efforts, resulting in wasted investments and missed opportunities to strengthen CI protection.
 - **Ineffective Response:** Inconsistent indicators can lead to delayed or ineffective response measures, making it challenging to mitigate the impact of disruptions swiftly.
 - **Compliance Challenges:** Failure to address the gap complicates compliance with regulatory requirements related to CI resilience. Organizations may struggle to demonstrate compliance, leading to potential legal and financial consequences.
 - **Diminished Public Trust:** A lack of transparency and consistency in resilience reporting can erode public trust in the ability of CI operators to protect critical services, potentially leading to public scepticism and unrest.
 - **Inaccurate Risk Management:** Inadequate alignment of resilience indicators hampers the accuracy of risk assessments, leaving organizations ill-prepared to manage potential threats effectively.
 - **Missed Improvement Opportunities:** Without standardized metrics, organizations may miss opportunities to improve CI resilience proactively, potentially exposing critical assets to avoidable risks.
- **CG4 – Lack of agreed Standards-based stress-testing procedures:** Along with poor alignment of indicators, there is also a lack of agreed stress-testing procedures that could foster the implementation of structured, standards-based CIR approaches. The capability gap identified in CG4 highlights a critical challenge in the CIP domain. This gap pertains to the absence of standardized stress-testing procedures, which are essential for assessing the resilience of CI systematically and consistently. Stress testing involves subjecting CI components to various scenarios, including cyberattacks, physical threats, or natural disasters, to evaluate their response and recovery capabilities. The lack of agreed-upon

standards for conducting such tests creates significant obstacles in implementing structured, standards-based approaches to CI resilience and hinders the implementation of structured critical incident response approaches. Without standardized procedures, CI entities struggle to assess their resilience adequately. Developing agreed-upon stress-testing procedures is essential for evaluating and enhancing the resilience of CI systems effectively.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Incomplete Resilience Assessments:** Without standardized stress-testing procedures, CI operators may conduct resilience assessments that are incomplete or inconsistent. This means that vulnerabilities in CI systems may go unnoticed, leaving critical assets exposed.
- **Inefficient Resource Allocation:** The absence of agreed-upon standards for stress testing can lead to inefficient resource allocation. Organizations may invest resources unevenly, focusing on some aspects of resilience while neglecting others, creating vulnerabilities.
- **Interoperability Challenges:** Inconsistent stress-testing procedures across different CI components and organizations can result in interoperability challenges. When systems or assets need to work together during a crisis, the lack of standardized testing can lead to compatibility issues, creating vulnerabilities.
- **Limited Benchmarking:** A lack of standardized procedures makes it difficult to benchmark CI resilience against industry standards or best practices. This means that CI operators may not have a clear understanding of how their resilience measures compare to recognized standards, potentially missing opportunities for improvement.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Unidentified Vulnerabilities:** The absence of standardized stress-testing procedures can result in unidentified vulnerabilities within CI systems. These vulnerabilities can be exploited by threat actors, leading to security breaches or disruptions.
- **Inefficient Resource Use:** CI operators may allocate resources inefficiently for resilience efforts due to the lack of standardized procedures. This can lead to wasted resources, missed vulnerabilities, and an inadequate overall security posture.
- **Inconsistent Resilience Levels:** Inconsistent testing approaches may lead to uneven levels of resilience across different CI components. Some areas may be well-prepared, while others remain vulnerable, creating weaknesses in the overall system.
- **Compliance Challenges:** CI operators may struggle to comply with regulatory requirements that mandate resilience testing. Non-compliance can result in legal and financial consequences.
- **Reduced Preparedness:** Incomplete resilience assessments and inefficient resource allocation can reduce the overall preparedness of CI systems to withstand and recover from disruptions. This can result in longer recovery times and increased impact during incidents.
- **Limited Collaboration:** Lack of standardized procedures can impede collaboration between organizations responsible for different CI components. This can hinder collective efforts to enhance overall resilience and create vulnerabilities in coordinated response efforts.
- **CG5 – Problems with the classification of IoT Devices:** In recent years there is a proliferation of IoT devices in CIs. However, the identification and classification of IoT-based assets is lagging behind the output of the suppliers and does not scale to account for the

increased diversity and complexity of the various classes of IoT devices. Currently, a “one size fits all” approach to securing IoT devices is applied, which is inadequate to address the vulnerabilities and risks associated with the growing number of connected devices. This capability gap sheds light on a pressing issue within the realm of CIP. IoT devices, while offering various advantages, pose a challenge when it comes to their identification, classification, and security management. The “one size fits all” approach is also inadequate to address the growing diversity and complexity of these assets. Failing to categorize and secure IoT devices properly can result in vulnerabilities that adversaries can exploit. Tailored approaches to IoT device security and classification are imperative to mitigate these risks.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Inaccurate Risk Assessment:** Inability to accurately identify and classify IoT devices makes it challenging to conduct precise risk assessments. CI operators may underestimate the security risks associated with specific devices, leaving vulnerabilities unaddressed.
- **Uniform Security Measures:** Applying a “one size fits all” security approach to IoT devices, regardless of their type or criticality, can result in uniform and potentially inadequate security measures. Some IoT devices may require stringent security controls, while others may not, leading to vulnerabilities.
- **Exploitable Weaknesses:** Incorrectly classified or unsecured IoT devices can serve as entry points for cyberattacks. Threat actors can exploit these weaknesses to gain access to critical systems, posing a significant security risk.
- **Inefficient Resource Allocation:** The lack of accurate classification hampers resource allocation. CI operators may invest resources disproportionately across IoT devices, potentially overspending on some and leaving critical ones under protected.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Increased Vulnerabilities:** Failure to accurately identify and classify IoT devices can lead to increased vulnerabilities within CI systems, increasing the likelihood of successful cyberattacks and disruptions.
 - **Inadequate Security Measures:** The use of a uniform security approach may result in inadequate protection for some IoT devices, leaving critical assets at risk of compromise.
 - **Compliance Challenges:** CI operators may struggle to comply with regulatory requirements that mandate specific security measures for IoT devices. Non-compliance can result in legal and financial penalties.
 - **Resource Inefficiency:** Inefficient allocation of security resources for IoT devices can lead to resource inefficiency, wasted investments, and suboptimal security postures.
 - **Reduced Risk Management:** The absence of accurate device classification hinders effective risk management efforts, making it challenging to prioritize security measures based on device criticality.
 - **Cyberattack Entry Points:** Unsecured or misclassified IoT devices can serve as potential entry points for cyberattacks, enabling threat actors to infiltrate CI systems and disrupt operations.
- **CG6 – Scalability in the Mitigation of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks:** DDoS attack mitigation efforts are not optimally scaling given the increase in the bandwidth that is nowadays available to end-users (e.g., multi-gigabit per second connectivity is now widely available to SMEs). Apart from bandwidth issues, there is also a need for mitigating measures that confront novel types of DDoS attacks, such as ways based on IoT devices and AI bots. CG6 therefore points to DDoS attacks being a pervasive threat, and their

mitigation is essential to ensure the availability and resilience of CI systems. However, as technology advances and the scale of attacks grows, addressing this gap becomes increasingly vital. Ensuring the scalability of DDoS mitigation is therefore crucial to preventing disruptions caused by these attacks.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Inadequate DDoS Protection:** The lack of scalable DDoS mitigation measures means that CI systems may have insufficient defences against large-scale DDoS attacks. Attackers can exploit this weakness to flood and disrupt critical services, compromising the availability and reliability of CI components.
- **Resource Drain:** Inefficient DDoS mitigation can drain CI operators' resources, both in terms of financial investment and human capital. Overcommitting resources to mitigate DDoS attacks can strain the overall operational capacity of CI organizations.
- **Exploitation of Novel Attack Vectors:** The emergence of novel DDoS attack vectors, such as those leveraging IoT devices and AI bots, presents new vulnerabilities. Without effective mitigation measures for these evolving threats, CI systems become susceptible to exploitation through unanticipated attack vectors.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Service Disruptions:** Failure to address scalability in DDoS mitigation can result in service disruptions within CI. This can have cascading effects, impacting users, businesses, and even public safety, depending on the sector affected.
- **Resource Overcommitment:** CI operators may overcommit resources in an attempt to mitigate DDoS attacks, diverting valuable assets away from other critical tasks and potentially exhausting budgets.
- **Prolonged Downtime:** Inadequate mitigation can lead to prolonged downtime of CI systems. Extended downtime can disrupt business operations, cause financial losses, and erode public trust in the reliability of CI services.
- **Increased Vulnerabilities:** Ignoring the scalability gap in DDoS mitigation may lead to increased vulnerabilities within CI systems. Attackers can exploit these weaknesses to launch successful DDoS attacks, potentially gaining unauthorized access to critical assets.
- **Public Safety Risks:** In sectors like transportation, energy, and healthcare, CI disruptions can pose risks to public safety. DDoS-induced operational disruptions can lead to accidents, emergencies, or other adverse situations.
- **Operational Inefficiency:** Inefficient resource allocation for DDoS mitigation can result in operational inefficiencies. CI organizations may find it challenging to balance security needs with other operational requirements, potentially hindering overall performance.
- **CG7 – Development and Deployment of AI-based systems:** Despite recent advances in AI systems and technologies, the potential of AI in CIP/CIR solutions remains underexploited. Moreover, there is still poor awareness on the part of employees and CIP/CIR vendors about AI capabilities. Likewise, existing solutions cannot deal effectively with AI-powered cyberattacks based on new adaptive AI technologies. As already outlined generative AI systems (e.g., like ChatGPT) provide opportunities to increase protection (e.g., based on the intelligent identification of attack patterns), yet they also introduce new potential vulnerabilities and attacks (e.g., due to the generation of new attack patterns). The capability gap identified in CG7 highlights a critical aspect of enhancing CIP and cyber resilience (CR). AI holds immense potential for bolstering CI defences, but the underutilization of AI, coupled with limited awareness and challenges posed by AI-driven cyber threats, represents a

significant gap in CIP strategies. Furthermore, existing solutions struggle to effectively counter AI-powered cyberattacks, introducing new vulnerabilities. Leveraging generative AI systems can enhance protection but must be done responsibly to avoid creating new attack vectors.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- Underutilized AI: Failure to fully utilize AI in CI protection means missing out on the advantages of AI-driven threat detection, response, and overall security enhancement. This underutilization leaves CI systems more vulnerable to sophisticated cyber threats.
- Limited Awareness: Poor awareness about AI capabilities among CI employees and vendors prevents them from recognizing and leveraging AI's potential to enhance security. This knowledge gap hampers the adoption of AI-based security measures.
- Ineffectiveness Against AI-Powered Threats: The emergence of AI-powered cyber threats, including adaptive AI technologies, introduces new vulnerabilities. Existing security solutions may struggle to effectively counter these evolving threats, rendering CI systems susceptible to AI-driven attacks.
- Generation of New Attack Patterns: While AI systems like generative AI can identify attack patterns intelligently, they can also generate new attack patterns. These new patterns may exploit vulnerabilities that traditional security measures fail to detect or address, introducing novel risks.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- Missed Threats: Failing to harness AI's capabilities can result in missed threat detection opportunities, allowing cyberattacks to evade detection and potentially cause significant harm to CI systems.
 - Resource Inefficiency: Inefficient resource allocation due to the underutilization of AI can lead to resource drain, as CI operators may allocate resources sub optimally for security tasks.
 - Reduced Cyber Resilience: Inadequate use of AI may limit CI systems' ability to adapt and respond effectively to rapidly evolving cyber threats, reducing overall cyber resilience.
 - Introduction of New Vulnerabilities: Ignoring the gap may lead to the introduction of new vulnerabilities through AI-generated attack patterns, putting CI assets at risk and making them susceptible to previously unseen attack vectors.
 - Competitive Disadvantage: Organizations that do not embrace AI may find themselves at a competitive disadvantage, both in terms of security effectiveness and operational efficiency, compared to their AI-empowered counterparts.
- **CG8 – Lack of Holistic Security Management Systems:** There is a lack of holistic security management solutions, which are operationally applicable and do not need to be customised from scratch. Furthermore, there is a lack of solutions that are uniform and operate across the large number of different stakeholders. The capability gap identified in CG8 underscores a critical deficiency in the realm of CIP. Holistic security management is essential for efficiently safeguarding CI assets, but the absence of readily applicable, standardized solutions presents significant challenges. The absence of holistic security management solutions tailored to the diverse needs of CI stakeholders complicates security operations. Customizing security solutions from scratch is time-consuming and inefficient. Standardized and operationally applicable security management systems that cater to the unique requirements of different stakeholders are, therefore, essential for comprehensive protection.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Inefficiency in Resource Allocation:** Without standardized, holistic security management systems, CI operators may allocate security resources inefficiently. This can result in underinvestment in critical areas and vulnerabilities in less-protected sectors or assets.
- **Fragmented Security Measures:** The absence of uniform security solutions can lead to fragmented security measures across different stakeholders and sectors. This fragmentation creates gaps and inconsistencies in security practices, leaving CI assets exposed to potential threats.
- **Complexity in Coordination:** Managing security operations without a unified system can be operationally complex. Coordinating security efforts among multiple stakeholders becomes challenging, potentially leading to delays in response and mitigation.
- **Customization Challenges:** Developing custom security solutions for each CI component or sector is time-consuming and costly. This customization can result in delays in implementing security measures and increase the risk of misconfigurations or vulnerabilities.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Inefficient Resource Allocation:** The lack of standardized security management systems may lead to inefficient resource allocation, causing CI operators to invest resources ineffectively and potentially leaving critical assets under protected.
- **Security Gaps:** Inconsistent security measures and a lack of uniformity can result in security gaps, where certain CI components or sectors receive inadequate protection. These gaps create opportunities for malicious actors to exploit vulnerabilities.
- **Operational Disruptions:** Managing security operations manually or through disjointed systems can disrupt operational workflows within CI. These disruptions may affect the continuity of CI services, leading to downtime and economic losses.
- **Fragmented Response:** Inconsistencies in security measures and a lack of uniformity can hinder coordinated responses to security incidents. This fragmentation may delay the detection and mitigation of threats, allowing them to escalate and cause more significant damage.
- **Increased Costs:** Developing custom security solutions for each CI component can be expensive, diverting financial resources from other critical areas of CI management. These increased costs can strain budgets and reduce overall resilience.
- **Lower Resilience:** Inadequate security management can undermine the overall resilience of CI. Lower resilience means that CI is less capable of withstanding and recovering from security incidents and disruptions, increasing the potential impact of cyber threats.
- **CG9 – Gaps in Emergency Management Processes:** There are significant gaps in standardised processes in cases of emergencies. For instance, there is a lack of universally agreed upon processes regarding communicating with external entities for emergencies and with public authorities regarding security/safety incidents. This capability gap highlights critical deficiencies in standardized processes for managing emergencies within the context of CIP. Effective emergency management is vital for the timely response to security incidents and ensuring the continuity of CI services. CI entities face significant challenges in standardized emergency management processes. The absence of universally agreed to processes for communicating with external entities during emergencies and reporting security incidents to public authorities can lead to inefficiencies during crisis situations. Streamlining emergency management processes is essential for timely and effective responses.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Delayed Response:** Inadequate emergency management processes can lead to delayed responses to security incidents and crises. Delays in containment and mitigation efforts provide malicious actors with more time to exploit vulnerabilities, potentially causing more extensive damage to CI assets.
- **Coordination Challenges:** The absence of standardized processes for coordinating with external entities, such as public authorities and first responders, can result in coordination challenges. This lack of coordination may hinder the effective mobilization of resources and expertise needed to manage security incidents efficiently.
- **Communication Breakdowns:** Gaps in communication processes with external entities can lead to communication breakdowns during emergencies. Failure to convey critical information in a timely and accurate manner can compromise public safety, exacerbate the impact of security incidents, and increase vulnerabilities.
- **Resource Inefficiency:** Inefficient resource allocation due to the lack of standardized processes can result in resource inefficiency. Misallocation of resources can strain budgets, diverting resources from other critical CI protection measures and leaving vulnerabilities unaddressed.
- **Cascading Effects:** Emergency management gaps can contribute to cascading effects within CI and across interconnected entities. A single security incident can trigger a chain reaction of disruptions, affecting supply chains, critical services, and the broader community. These cascading effects can amplify vulnerabilities and their consequences.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Increased Vulnerability:** Inadequate emergency management processes can increase CI's vulnerability to security incidents, making it easier for malicious actors to exploit weaknesses and disrupt critical services.
 - **Escalation of Incidents:** Delayed responses and coordination challenges can lead to the escalation of security incidents, resulting in more extensive damage and longer recovery times.
 - **Compromised Public Safety:** Communication breakdowns with public authorities and external entities can compromise public safety by hindering the dissemination of crucial information and the timely response to emergencies.
 - **Resource Wastage:** Inefficient resource allocation can lead to resource wastage, increasing operational costs, and diverting resources from essential security measures.
 - **Cascading Effects:** Gaps in emergency management processes can contribute to cascading effects, amplifying the consequences of security incidents and potentially causing economic losses and disruptions to critical services.
 - **Reduced Resilience:** A CI's overall resilience is compromised when emergency management processes are inadequate. Lower resilience means that CI is less capable of withstanding and recovering from security incidents and emergencies, increasing its susceptibility to vulnerabilities.
- **CG10 – Inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats:** There is a lack of dynamic and intelligent solutions that can deal with ever evolving and dynamically changing threats, proactively and adaptively. Adaptive, AI-based solutions could provide the required intelligence, yet they are still not widely developed or used in the CIP/CIR domain. There is, therefore, a need for evolving knowledge modelling and a knowledge basis in directions that address the evolution of the threat landscape. This capability gap highlights the need for more advanced and dynamic solutions to counter emerging threats effectively. The dynamic nature of evolving threats poses a formidable challenge to CIP. Conventional solutions struggle to

adapt proactively and intelligently to these constantly changing threats. Embracing adaptive, AI-based solutions is necessary to anticipate and respond to evolving threats effectively. Evolving knowledge modelling and threat landscape analysis are essential components of addressing this capability gap.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Detection Lag:** Inability to adapt quickly to evolving threats results in a detection lag. Threats may go unnoticed, and attackers can exploit vulnerabilities within CI systems before countermeasures are activated, increasing the risk of successful attacks.
- **Ineffective Response:** Without dynamic and intelligent solutions, responses to emerging threats may be ineffective or delayed. This ineffectiveness allows attackers to continue their activities, potentially causing extensive damage and disruption to CI operations.
- **Resource Misallocation:** In the absence of proactive threat adaptation, resources may be misallocated. Critical areas of CI may be underinvested in, leaving them vulnerable, while less critical areas receive unnecessary attention, leading to resource inefficiency.
- **Limited Resilience:** An inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats reduces the overall resilience of CI. Resilience relies on adaptive responses to disruptions, and vulnerability to evolving threats weakens CI's capacity to recover from incidents.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Increased Vulnerabilities:** Failing to address the gap in coping with dynamically evolving threats can result in increased vulnerabilities within CI, making it easier for malicious actors to exploit weaknesses and launch successful attacks.
 - **Delayed or Ineffective Responses:** The inability to adapt quickly can lead to delayed or ineffective responses to emerging threats. This delay provides attackers with more time to carry out their activities, potentially causing greater damage and disruption.
 - **Resource Inefficiency:** Limited ability to prioritize and allocate resources effectively can lead to resource inefficiency. Critical areas may lack the necessary protections, while non-critical areas receive excessive attention, straining budgets and diverting resources from essential security measures.
 - **Reduced Resilience:** CI's overall resilience is compromised when it cannot effectively address dynamic threats.
 - **Unpredictable Consequences:** Emerging threats can have unpredictable consequences, including cascading effects that disrupt interconnected value chains and critical services. Failure to address the gap may result in unanticipated disruptions.
- **CG11 – Poor Awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges:** There is generally a lack of awareness regarding contemporary CIP/CIR requirements, such as needing to understand cascading events, preparedness against new natural and anthropic risks, and complex cyber resilience issues. Hence, there is a need for training security teams and developing new talent as part of a broader cultural shift that considers the latest CIP/CIR challenges such as evolving threats, novel forms of attacks and disruptions, and the need to consider interconnected infrastructures and cascading effects. This gap highlights the critical need to enhance awareness and understanding of contemporary critical infrastructure protection and resilience (CIP/CIR) requirements, with an emphasis on the importance of education, training, and cultural shifts within the context of CIP/CIR. A general lack of awareness about contemporary CIP/CIR requirements is a significant concern. Complex cyber resilience issues, cascading events, and preparedness against new risks are often overlooked. Developing talent

and training security teams are pivotal for creating a culture of awareness that acknowledges evolving threats, novel attack forms, and the interconnectivity of CIs.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Lack of Understanding:** Poor awareness means that CI operators and personnel may not fully understand the contemporary threats and challenges facing CI. This lack of understanding can lead to inadequate protection measures.
- **Ineffective Risk Mitigation:** Without an awareness of modern CIP/CIR challenges, CI operators may struggle to effectively identify, assess, and mitigate risks. This can result in vulnerabilities that are not adequately addressed.
- **Cyber Vulnerabilities:** In the context of cybersecurity, a lack of awareness about evolving cyber threats and cyber resilience can leave CI systems vulnerable to such attacks. Operators may not implement the latest security measures, leaving systems exposed.
- **Cascading Effects:** Poor awareness of cascading events and interconnected infrastructures means that CI operators may not anticipate how disruptions in one sector can propagate across others. This lack of awareness can result in vulnerabilities to cascading effects.
- **Anthropic Risks:** Neglecting awareness of anthropic risks, such as intentional acts of sabotage or terrorism, leaves CI vulnerable to these threats. Lack of preparedness and protection measures can lead to vulnerabilities.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Increased Vulnerability:** Failing to address the gap in awareness of modern CIP/CIR challenges increases CI's vulnerability to various threats and risks, making it more susceptible to disruptions.
- **Ineffective Risk Mitigation:** Poor awareness can lead to ineffective risk mitigation efforts, leaving CI with unaddressed vulnerabilities that can be exploited by malicious actors.
- **Cyberattacks and Vulnerabilities:** Inadequate awareness of cyber threats and cyber resilience principles can result in cyberattacks and vulnerabilities within CI systems, potentially causing data breaches, operational disruptions, and financial losses.
- **Cascading Effects:** Without an awareness of cascading events and interconnected infrastructures, CIs may be ill-prepared to handle disruptions that propagate across different sectors, leading to extended downtime and service interruptions.
- **Risk of Sabotage:** Neglecting awareness of anthropic risks, such as intentional sabotage or terrorism, increases the risk of such incidents occurring within CI, potentially causing significant damage, loss of life, and public safety concerns.
- **Stagnation:** A failure to address the awareness gap can lead to stagnation in CIP efforts, as organizations continue with outdated practices and inadequate risk mitigation measures. This can result in a lack of resilience in the face of evolving threats.

In addition to the identified capability gaps (CG1 to CG11), there are several other fundamental gaps that warrant attention in the realm of CIP/CIR. Addressing these gaps alongside the previously mentioned needs can provide a more comprehensive framework for enhancing CIP/CIR.

- **CG12 –Adaptive Threat Intelligence:** There is a gap in the ability to adapt threat intelligence mechanisms to rapidly evolving threats. Current systems often struggle to keep up with emerging threat vectors and require more adaptive and real-time threat intelligence capabilities. Adaptive threat intelligence is critical in the context of CIP because it involves the continuous monitoring and analysis of evolving threats. Threat actors are becoming increasingly sophisticated, and they constantly develop new tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs). To effectively defend against these threats, it is essential to have threat

intelligence mechanisms that can adapt in real-time. The gap in adaptive threat intelligence capabilities, therefore, poses a significant risk to CIP. Threat intelligence mechanisms that cannot rapidly adapt to emerging threats leave vulnerabilities unaddressed. As threat actors become increasingly sophisticated, continuous monitoring and real-time analysis of evolving threats are imperative. Adaptive threat intelligence is essential to staying ahead of adversaries in the ever-changing threat landscape.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- **Incomplete Threat Visibility:** Without adaptive threat intelligence, CI operators may lack a comprehensive view of emerging threats. This incomplete picture hinders their ability to detect and respond to new attack vectors effectively.
- **Delayed Identification and Response:** In the absence of adaptive threat intelligence, the slow identification and response to rapidly evolving threats create a critical window of opportunity for threat actors to exploit vulnerabilities within CI systems. This delay significantly elevates the likelihood of successful cyberattacks, allowing threat actors to execute sophisticated and targeted attacks before effective countermeasures can be deployed.
- **Ineffective Mitigation:** Traditional threat intelligence often relies on historical data and known signatures. As a result, it may struggle to identify and mitigate zero-day vulnerabilities and novel attack techniques used by more sophisticated adversaries.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- **Cyberattacks Targeting Critical Infrastructure:** Without the ability to adapt quickly to evolving threats, CI systems are at a heightened risk of being targeted by cyberattacks. Attackers, especially those with sophisticated tactics, may exploit this gap to breach CI networks, leading to service disruptions, operational downtime, and potentially causing widespread public safety hazards. For example, a cyberattack targeting a power grid could result in widespread power outages, affecting businesses, hospitals, and residential areas.
- **Data Breaches and Compromise of Sensitive Information:** In the absence of adaptive threat intelligence, sensitive data within CI systems becomes vulnerable to breaches. This could lead to the compromise of confidential information, including personal data, financial records, and classified government information. Such breaches not only compromise individual privacy but can also have severe implications for national security and public trust.
- **Economic Fallout and Instability:** Successful cyberattacks on CI can trigger significant economic repercussions. The resulting financial losses, including repair costs, operational disruptions, and potential legal liabilities, can have a detrimental impact on businesses, governments, and individuals. Furthermore, heightened risks may lead to increased insurance premiums, creating financial strain for CI operators and potentially impacting the broader economy.
- **Erosion of Public Trust and Confidence:** Inadequate protection of critical infrastructure can erode public trust in CI providers and the reliability of essential services. Frequent cyber incidents and disruptions can lead to scepticism among the public, causing individuals to question the security and resilience of CI systems. The loss of public trust can significantly affect the reputation of CI operators and the overall credibility of public services, leading to decreased public cooperation and support.

- National Security Threats and Geopolitical Vulnerabilities: Vulnerable critical infrastructure poses significant national security risks, especially when targeted by nation-state actors or sophisticated cybercriminal groups. Exploiting the gap in adaptive threat intelligence can offer malicious actors' opportunities to disrupt essential services, compromise sensitive government operations, or even launch coordinated attacks on a nation's critical infrastructure. Such vulnerabilities can undermine a nation's geopolitical stability and compromise its ability to defend against external threats.
- **CG13 - Incident Response Coordination:** Coordinating incident response across multiple CI entities and government agencies can be challenging. A gap exists in the development of standardized incident response protocols that ensure seamless coordination during crises. In essence, it highlights the absence of a well-structured and unified approach to responding to cyber incidents and threats within the CI landscape. Coordinating incident responses across multiple CI entities and government agencies is a complex task. Without standardized incident response protocols and coordination mechanisms, effective collaboration during crises becomes even more challenging. Streamlining incident response coordination through standardized protocols is crucial to ensuring seamless responses to cyber incidents.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- Ineffective Communication: Without standardized incident response protocols and coordination mechanisms, communication between CI entities and government agencies can be disjointed and inefficient. This can lead to a lack of timely information sharing, hindering the ability to assess and respond to threats effectively.
- Delayed Response: In the event of a cyberattack or other critical incident, delays in response can occur due to the absence of coordinated procedures. Cyber threats evolve rapidly, and any delay in responding to an incident can exacerbate its impact.
- Inefficient Resource Allocation: Without standardized protocols, resource allocation can be haphazard. Ineffective resource allocation can lead to wasted efforts or insufficient resources devoted to critical tasks, increasing vulnerability to cyber threats.
- Missed Threat Indicators: Inconsistent incident response coordination may result in the overlooking of critical threat indicators. This can allow cyber adversaries to operate undetected within CI systems, posing a significant security risk.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- Increased Cybersecurity Risks: Inadequate incident response coordination increases the likelihood of successful cyberattacks on CI, including energy, transportation, healthcare, and financial systems. Such attacks can disrupt services, compromise sensitive data, and undermine public trust.
- Extended Downtime: Delays in incident response can prolong the downtime of critical systems, impacting upon essential services and the economy. Extended outages can lead to financial losses and damage a nation's overall resilience.
- Public Safety Threats: In sectors like healthcare and transportation, inefficient incident response coordination can pose direct threats to public safety. Service disruptions or accidents caused by cyberattacks can result in injuries or loss of life.
- National Security Risks: In cases where CI is intertwined with national security, such as defence systems or emergency response networks, inadequate coordination can pose significant national security risks.

- Loss of Public Trust: Repeated incidents and ineffective response coordination can erode public trust in the ability of CI providers and government agencies to safeguard essential services.
- Economic Impact: The economic consequences of unaddressed gaps in incident response coordination can be substantial. Costs associated with cyber incidents, recovery efforts, and potential litigation can strain resources.
- **CG14 - Emerging Technology Adoption:** Embracing emerging technologies like AI, quantum computing, and blockchain for security purposes is lagging. A gap exists in adopting and integrating these technologies into CIP strategies. It highlights a hesitancy or delay in harnessing the potential of these technologies for enhancing security and resilience. The slow adoption and integration of these technologies in CIP strategies create vulnerabilities. Embracing these technologies is vital for staying ahead of evolving threats. Their potential for enhancing security and resilience should not be underestimated, but careful integration and awareness are essential to prevent potential vulnerabilities associated with these technologies.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- Outdated Security Measures: Failing to adopt emerging technologies means relying on older, potentially less effective security measures. This can make CI more vulnerable to evolving cyber threats that exploit known weaknesses.
- Limited Threat Detection: Emerging technologies like AI can significantly improve threat detection and predictive analytics. A failure to adopt these technologies can result in slower and less accurate threat detection, leaving CI exposed to sophisticated cyberattacks.
- Inefficient Resource Utilization: Without leveraging technologies like blockchain for secure data management and quantum computing for advanced cryptography, resource utilization may be suboptimal. This inefficiency can lead to gaps in resource allocation for security efforts.
- Resistance to Innovation: Resistance or reluctance to embrace emerging technologies can hinder innovation and the development of more effective security solutions. CI providers may therefore miss out on opportunities to stay ahead of cyber threats.
- Missed Efficiency Gains: Emerging technologies often offer efficiency gains, both in terms of operational processes and security. Failing to adopt these technologies can result in missed opportunities to enhance overall infrastructure resilience.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- Increased Cyber Risk: The gap in adopting emerging technologies can lead to heightened cyber risks. CI providers may struggle to defend against increasingly cyber threats, potentially resulting in breaches and service disruptions.
- Loss of Competitive Advantage: Entities that fail to adopt innovative technologies may lose their competitive advantage in terms of security, operational efficiency, and adaptability to emerging threats.
- Missed Cost Savings: Emerging technologies can streamline processes and reduce operational costs. Not embracing these technologies may lead to higher expenses in maintaining and securing CI.
- Reduced Resilience: In the face of evolving threats and challenges, the reduced adoption of emerging technologies can result in decreased resilience. CI may thus be less capable of recovering from incidents and disruptions.

- Regulatory and Compliance Risks: Emerging technologies often come with regulatory implications. Failure to adopt them may lead to compliance risks and penalties, particularly in industries with stringent security requirements.
- **CG15 - Rapid Recovery Strategies:** While there is a focus on threat prevention and detection, there is a gap in developing rapid recovery strategies. Having robust plans for quickly restoring operations after an incident is crucial for minimizing downtime. The gap pertains to the lack of emphasis on developing and implementing rapid recovery strategies within the context of CIP. While there is often a significant focus on threat prevention and detection, ensuring that effective plans are in place to restore operations swiftly following an incident is equally important, where a lack of such plans can lead to prolonged downtime following incidents. Having robust plans for quickly restoring operations is critical for minimizing the impact of disruptions. Ensuring that recovery strategies are an integral part of CIP efforts is essential for resilience in the face of cyber threats and other incidents.

Contribution to Vulnerabilities in CI:

- Extended Downtime: Failing to prioritize rapid recovery strategies can lead to extended downtime in the event of an incident, whether it's a cyberattack, natural disaster, or another disruptive event. Prolonged downtime can have severe economic and societal impacts.
- Economic Losses: Lengthy recovery times can result in substantial economic losses for CI providers and the broader economy. Industries that rely on CI services may also suffer financial repercussions.
- Increased Vulnerability: During the recovery phase, CI systems may be in a vulnerable state, making them susceptible to further attacks or disruptions. Without rapid recovery plans, these vulnerabilities persist for longer periods.
- Resource Misallocation: Inadequate recovery planning may lead to resource misallocation, with CI providers struggling to allocate the necessary resources efficiently to restore operations.
- Loss of Trust: Prolonged service disruptions can erode public trust in CI providers. Such trust is crucial for the smooth functioning of society and the economy.

Potential Consequences of not addressing the gap:

- Economic Impact: Extended downtime can result in significant economic losses, affecting CI providers, businesses, and communities that rely on these services.
- Operational Disruptions: Failure to address rapid recovery strategies can lead to prolonged operational disruptions.
- Security Risks: Longer recovery times may expose CI systems to additional security risks, including further cyberattacks or physical threats.
- Public Discontent: Prolonged service disruptions can lead to public discontent, potentially resulting in protests, legal action, or loss of customers for CI providers.
- Regulatory Scrutiny: Regulatory bodies may impose penalties or stricter regulations on CI providers who are unable to meet recovery time objectives.

The Capability Gaps Analysis conducted by the EU-CIP Consortium revealed critical vulnerabilities in the realm of CIP. These vulnerabilities stem from challenges such as poor automation, lack of control over interconnected assets, misalignment of resilience indicators, absence of standardized stress-testing procedures, issues with IoT device classification, scalability concerns in DDoS

mitigation, underutilization of AI, lack of holistic security management systems, gaps in emergency management processes, and difficulty in coping with evolving threats. These gaps contribute to vulnerabilities that include delayed response to cyber threats, increased risk of cascading failures, inefficient resource allocation, heightened exposure to unforeseen events, potential security breaches, service disruptions, and compromised public safety. Addressing these gaps is vital to fortify the resilience, security, and integrity of CI in an increasingly complex and interconnected world.

8.2. Annex C.2: Stakeholders input

Beyond the above-listed general capabilities needs and gaps that are applicable to all CIP sectors, EU-CIP partners have expertise in different sectors and have identified capabilities needs and gaps linked to specific sectors.

The workshop brought together a diverse group of experts from the consortium to discuss challenges and future visions in the CIP ecosystem. The workshop was hosted by the project's coordinator, Emilia Gugliandolo and highlighted the importance of understanding capability needs and gaps in CIP.

The workshop kicked off with a roundtable discussion where participants shared visionary statements regarding CIP/CIR by 2030.

The key takeaways from the workshop included:

- **Integration and Avoiding Silos:** There was a consensus on the need to break down silos between different infrastructures. Participants stressed the interconnectedness of critical systems and the importance of addressing cascading effects in supply chains.
- **Trends in CIP:** Emerging trends in CIP were discussed, with a focus on increased cybersecurity measures and the adoption of advanced technologies like AI.
- **Airport Challenges:** Challenges related to cybersecurity at airports were highlighted, underlining the close relationship between cyber assets and physical security. Topics such as safety baselines, emerging threats like AI attacks, and real-time knowledge sharing were also mentioned.
- **Legislation and Proposals:** Participants discussed new legislation and proposals related to CIP, including the NIS2 Resilience Critical Entities Directive and the proposed Cyber Resilience Act. The need for improved implementation was emphasized.
- **Water Sector Priorities:** Priorities in the water sector included digitalization, cybersecurity in water treatment plants, risk management, and coordinated solutions during emergencies.
- **Port Resilience:** The importance of reinforcing ports as resilient infrastructures was discussed in light of evolving threats. The aim is to ensure the continuity of critical operations and contribute to overall supply chain resilience.
- **Re-evaluating Vulnerability Assessments:** The need to redesign risk and vulnerability assessments considering geopolitical situations and climate change impacts was highlighted, aligning with the theme of integrated resilience.

The key takeaways from the EU-CIP workshop shed light on the pressing needs and gaps in CIP, emphasizing the importance of a holistic and integrated approach to safeguarding critical systems.

Firstly, the call for integration and avoiding silos underscores the necessity of breaking down barriers between different CIs. This integration is crucial for addressing the identified capability gaps, such as the Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness (CG2) and Poor Alignment of Resilience Indicators (CG3). By promoting interoperability and a shared understanding of dependencies, CIP can better manage cascading effects across supply chains and interconnected infrastructures.

The discussion on Trends in CIP aligns with the need to adopt Emerging Technology (CG14) and improve awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges (CG11). As emerging trends emphasize increased cybersecurity measures and the adoption of advanced technologies like AI, it becomes evident that embracing these innovations is essential for bridging existing gaps. However, the hesitancy in Emerging Technology Adoption (CG14) highlights the need for regulatory frameworks, like the proposed Cyber Resilience Act, to ensure their safe and effective integration.

The focus on Airport Challenges highlights the close link between cyber assets and physical security, touching upon the need for Rapid Recovery Strategies (CG15) and Adaptive Threat Intelligence (CG12) to counter emerging threats like AI attacks. Real-time knowledge sharing and collaboration can address the Incident Response Coordination gap (CG13) by facilitating timely responses to evolving threats.

Within the Water Sector Priorities, the emphasis on digitalization, cybersecurity in water treatment plants, risk management, and coordinated solutions during emergencies resonates with the broader needs of CIP, including Security Risk Assessment (CG2) and Lack of Holistic Security Management Systems (CG8).

Reinforcing ports as resilient infrastructures aligns with the need for Rapid Recovery Strategies (CG15) and the ability to cope with dynamically evolving threats (CG10). Ensuring the continuity of critical operations within ports contributes to overall supply chain resilience, addressing vulnerabilities in the interconnected infrastructure.

Lastly, the call to re-evaluate vulnerability assessments in light of geopolitical situations and climate change impacts highlights the need to adapt security strategies dynamically. This aligns with the call for Adaptive Threat Intelligence (CG12) and the ability to cope with dynamically evolving threats (CG10), emphasizing the importance of continuously evolving knowledge modelling and risk assessment practices to ensure integrated resilience in the face of evolving challenges.

In summary, the key takeaways from the EU-CIP workshop emphasize the critical need for integrated approaches to address identified capability gaps in CIP. This integration should encompass not only technological advancements but also regulatory frameworks and collaborative efforts to ensure the resilience of interconnected critical systems.

8.3. Annex C.3: Gaps and Needs prioritisation from the users' point of view

The second part of the workshop focused on **prioritizing capability gaps**. Notable points from this discussion included:

- Emphasis on transparency and customization in addressing interconnectedness and cascading effects in security management.
- Prioritization of capability needs related to prediction of threats, improved management of security services, and the integration of cyber and physical security.

- The telco sector's need for better integration of security tools with Information Security Management (ISM) systems.
- Advocacy for addressing gaps in emergency management due to siloing issues.
- Capacity needs in the finance sector, including adaptability and improved detection capabilities, while focusing on gaps in advanced AI-based systems development and coping with evolving threats.
- Recognition of the critical issue of talent shortage in cybersecurity teams, with a priority on talent availability and other gap areas.

The participants found the discussion insightful and valuable for their respective reports, with plans to continue exploring specific aspects in future workshops.

Participants also engaged in a thorough discussion to prioritize the capability gaps identified in CIP. Below is an extended perspective on how these priorities align with the previously mentioned gaps and needs:

1. **Transparency and Customization:** The emphasis on transparency and customization in addressing interconnectedness and cascading effects in security management directly corresponds to the Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness (CG2) and Poor Alignment of Resilience Indicators (CG3) gaps. Prioritizing this aspect means recognizing the importance of tailoring security measures to the specific dependencies and vulnerabilities within CI networks.
2. **Prediction of Threats:** Prioritizing capability needs related to threat prediction is closely linked to the Inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats (CG10) gap. Developing predictive capabilities can help CI entities stay ahead of evolving threats, especially when threat actors constantly develop new tactics and procedures. This aligns with the broader context of enhancing security through AI and emerging technologies.
3. **Managed Security Services:** The emphasis on improved managed security services echoes the Poor Automation (CG1) gap. Enhancing automation in threat detection and response is critical for achieving fast protection and recovery from cyber-attacks. Integrating managed security services can significantly contribute to closing this automation loop.
4. **Integration of Cyber and Physical Security:** The prioritization of integrating cyber and physical security aligns with the need to address cascading effects and the Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness (CG2) gap. When cyber and physical security are seamlessly integrated, it becomes easier to manage the dependencies and vulnerabilities that could lead to cascading failures in CI.
5. **Telco Sector Integration:** The telco sector's need for better integration of security tools with Information Security Management (ISM) systems is a practical response to the Lack of Holistic Security Management Systems (CG8) gap. Achieving seamless integration between security tools and ISM systems can provide a holistic view of security across diverse stakeholders and technologies.
6. **Emergency Management:** Advocating for addressing gaps in emergency management due to siloing issues directly corresponds to Gaps in Emergency Management Processes (CG9). Standardized incident response protocols and communication with external entities are essential to ensuring a coordinated and efficient response during crises.
7. **Finance Sector Capacities:** The capacity needs in the finance sector, including adaptability and improved detection capabilities, are closely tied to the need to cope with dynamically evolving threats (CG10) and the slow adoption of emerging technologies (CG14). Prioritizing adaptability and advanced AI-based systems development can help the finance sector stay resilient against evolving threats.

8. **Talent Shortage Recognition:** Recognizing the critical issue of a talent shortage in cybersecurity teams is essential for addressing Poor Awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges (CG11). Prioritizing talent availability and training can bridge this gap by ensuring that security teams are well-prepared to tackle contemporary challenges and emerging threats.

In summary, the prioritization of these capability gaps reflects a holistic approach to strengthening CIP. By addressing these gaps, organizations can work toward enhancing their resilience, adopting advanced technologies, and fostering collaboration across sectors, ultimately contributing to the security and stability of CI networks.

Prioritizing the capability gaps in CIP based on their alignment with EU program Horizon Europe's calls, topics, and funded projects can help ensure that limited resources are allocated effectively. In the following a prioritization of the identified gaps, giving more weight to those that are less covered by Horizon Europe initiatives, is presented:

1. **CG12 – Adaptive Threat Intelligence:** Given the increasing sophistication of threat actors and the need for real-time adaptation, this gap should be a top priority. While Horizon Europe may cover aspects of threat intelligence, a specific focus on real-time adaptation and continuous monitoring of evolving threats would be essential.
2. **CG15 - Rapid Recovery Strategies:** Rapid recovery after a cyber incident is crucial to minimize downtime. Although Horizon Europe emphasizes cybersecurity, there may be less focus on rapid recovery strategies. Prioritizing this gap can help CI entities bounce back more quickly from attacks.
3. **CG7 – Development and Deployment of AI-based systems:** While Horizon Europe acknowledges the potential of AI, there may be gaps in addressing AI-powered cyberattacks and ensuring awareness within the sector. Prioritizing AI-based solutions can enhance protection against emerging threats.
4. **CG2 – Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness:** This gap relates to addressing dependencies and interconnectedness between CI assets. While Horizon Europe promotes collaboration and interconnectivity, a specific focus on control mechanisms may be lacking.
5. **CG14 - Emerging Technology Adoption:** Horizon Europe encourages the adoption of emerging technologies, but there may still be gaps in their integration into CIP strategies. Prioritizing this gap can help accelerate the adoption of technologies like AI, quantum computing, and blockchain.
6. **CG4 – Lack of agreed Standards-based stress-testing procedures:** Standardized stress-testing procedures may not receive sufficient attention in existing initiatives. Prioritizing this gap can ensure the development of structured, standards-based approaches for CIP.
7. **CG10 – Inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats:** While Horizon Europe promotes innovation, addressing dynamically evolving threats may require more focused efforts. Prioritizing adaptive, AI-based solutions can provide the intelligence needed to tackle evolving threats effectively.
8. **CG13 - Incident Response Coordination:** Horizon Europe may support incident response efforts, but the emphasis on standardized protocols and coordination mechanisms may need more attention. Prioritizing this gap can ensure a well-structured and unified approach to cyber incident response.
9. **CG11 – Poor Awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges:** Awareness about contemporary CIP/CIR requirements may not be fully covered by existing initiatives. Prioritizing training and talent development can help address this gap and prepare security teams for evolving challenges.

10. **CG9 – Gaps in Emergency Management Processes:** While Horizon Europe promotes cooperation, there may still be gaps in standardized emergency management processes. Prioritizing this gap can improve communication and coordination during critical incidents.

By prioritizing these capability gaps based on their alignment with Horizon Europe's coverage, CI entities and policymakers can strategically allocate resources and funding to address the most pressing needs that may not be sufficiently covered by existing initiatives. This approach can enhance the overall resilience of CI networks in Europe.

8.4. Annex C.4: Interdependencies and Cross-Cutting Themes

Exploring the intricate interdependencies between different capability needs and gaps within the domain of CIP is crucial for crafting comprehensive and efficient strategies to bolster the resilience of CIs. The CIP workshop served as a platform for experts to delve into these intricate relationships, unveiling the complex challenges that confront the CIP ecosystem.

One prominent theme that emerged from the discussions was the interconnected nature of CI systems. The call to break down silos between distinct infrastructures, as highlighted throughout the workshop, underscored the necessity of addressing cascading effects in supply chains, as noted by another participant. The fact that one infrastructure's stability can hinge on the reliability of another underscores the significance of integrated and all-encompassing approaches to CIP.

Furthermore, the workshop discussions illuminated the close nexus between cybersecurity and physical security, particularly in settings like airports. The integration of these two domains stands as a crucial facet of safeguarding critical assets. Consequently, tackling capability gaps related to both cybersecurity and physical security becomes inherently linked, underscoring the importance of comprehensive solutions that effectively bridge these domains.

The workshop also emphasized the growing importance of advanced technologies like AI. Discussions on trends in CIP, including AI adoption, emphasized its significance in addressing various capability needs, such as bolstering detection capabilities and adapting to evolving threats. Integrating AI-based systems into CIP not only enhances detection and response but also introduces fresh challenges, such as the development and management of advanced AI-based systems. This interdependency highlights the necessity for holistic strategies that account for the deployment and governance of AI technologies within the context of CIP.

Additionally, the acknowledged shortage of talent in cybersecurity teams has wide-reaching repercussions. It directly affects the availability of skilled personnel (a capability need) while simultaneously impacting upon the overall cybersecurity posture. This can potentially exacerbate gaps related to coping with rapidly evolving threats. This observation underscores the multifaceted nature of capability needs and gaps, where addressing one issue can have a cascading impact on others.

The workshop discussions highlighted how various facets of CIP are intricately connected, emphasizing the need for holistic approaches that acknowledge these interdependencies to enhance the resilience of CIs. As the CIP landscape continues to evolve, understanding these interconnections will be paramount for navigating the complex challenges it presents.

9. Annex D: Market analysis

9.1. Annex D.1: Market size & growth drivers

According to recent research reports (e.g., Polaris Market Research illustrated in Figure 5) the Critical Infrastructure Protect (CIP) market has a growing momentum. For instance, according to Polaris Market Research, the CIP market was valued at USD 132.42 billion in 2021 and is expected to reach USD 177.35 billion by 2030 i.e., to exhibit a growth at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 3.4%, during the forecast period. This growth potential is also reflected in other market research reports that calculate the CIP market differently in terms of sector and solutions scope. For instance, a recent report by Triton Market Research⁷ estimated that the global CIP market will exhibit a CAGR of 6.89% in the forecasting duration between 2021 and 2028 i.e., from \$72.76 billion in revenue in 2020 to \$129.07 billion by 2028.

The growth of the CIP market is mainly driven by the proliferating cyber-security challenges, which emerge as a result of the rapid digitization of various CIs. As a prominent example, in many different sectors, OT (Operational Technology) is converging with IT, and therefore there is a need for cybersecurity solutions for industrial automation systems like SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition). Moreover, most CI providers have ridden the wave of cloud and Internet of Things services, which creates new cyber-security challenges. The pace of this digitization has further increased following the COVID19 pandemic outbreak, which gave rise to new digitization trends like remote work and BYOD (Bring Your Own Device).

Figure 5: Critical Infrastructure Protection Market Overview (Source: Polaris Market Research).

The CIP growth is also propelled by concerns about climate change, which will potentially have a significant impact on different types of CIs and critical entities. Specifically, the proliferation of climatic disaster events represents a serious challenge for CIP systems at regional and national levels.

⁷ <https://www.tritonmarketresearch.com/reports/critical-infrastructure-protection-market>

Another factor that drives growth is the need for compliance with existing and emerging regulations, such as the CER (Critical Entities Resilience) directive in Europe. Furthermore, the need for professionals with advanced cybersecurity skills for domains like the cloud and IoT is driving the demand for CIP-related services.

9.2. Annex D.2: Various market segments

The market of CIP solutions includes the following types of solutions (Figure 6):

- Physical Safety and Security
- Physical Identity and Access Control Systems
- Perimeter Intrusion Detection Systems
- Video Surveillance Systems
- Physical Security Information Management (PSIM)
- Screening and Scanning
- Cybersecurity Encryption
- Network Access Controls and Firewalls
- Threat Intelligence solutions
- Vehicle Identification Systems
- Building Management Systems
- Secure Communications Systems
- SCADA Security
- CBRNE (Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear, and high yield Explosives) Products.

Figure 6: Prominent Types of Solutions in the CIP Market

Likewise, the market includes CIP services such as (Figure 7):

- Risk Management Services
- CIP Design Services
- CIP Integration, and Consultation Services
- Managed Services
- Maintenance and Support Services
- Training Services

Figure 7: Segments of the CIP Services Market

Finally, the market can be segmented per CI sector, including Banking and Finance, Government Services, (Tele-)Communication/Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), Energy/Electricity, Health Services, Transportation/Logistics/Distribution, Water (supply), Food, and Environmental Protection.

9.2.1. Annex D.2.1: EU market

Figure 8 illustrates findings from Triton Market Research the growth potential of the CIP sector in key European countries like Germany, France, Italy, and the UK. The growth of the market is propelled by similar drivers/factors as the global market, including the rising demand for cyber-security, new regulations, and mitigating against climate disasters. The CAGR of the expected growth is 6.76%, which is more or less similar to the growth of the global market that is predicted by the same research company.

Figure 8: Europe's CIP Market

Some of the most prominent vendors in the European market are Honeywell International Inc, Hexagon AB, Lockheed Martin Corporation, Northrop Grumman Corporation, Raytheon Company, General Dynamics Corporation, General Electric Company, Waterfall Security Solutions Ltd, Kaspersky Lab Inc, Airbus SETeltronic, Axis Communications, Ericsson AB, and McAfee Inc (TPG Capital). Note that these include non-European vendors with an established presence and significant footprint in the European market. However, the list includes major European players as well such as Hexagon and Ericsson, both of which are headquartered in Sweden.

A review of the specific solutions provided by individual vendors will follow in subsequent roadmaps.

9.2.2. Annex D.2.2: The market beyond

Europe is the region with the second highest market share globally, yet the European market share is around half that of the market share of North America. This is illustrated in a recent report by Future Market Research⁸ and is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: CIP Market Share Per Region (source: Market Future Research, May 2023)

⁸ <https://www.marketresearchfuture.com/>

The same report revealed that the Asia-Pacific region is expected to experience the highest growth rate over the next ten years when compared to other regions. China in particular has the largest footprint and share in the Asia-Pacific market, while India seems to be the fastest growing segment. The number of un-filled jobs offering work from home is estimated to reach 3.5 million. Additionally, according to the report of the Australian Strategic Policy Institute (ASPI) in 2019, it is found that the Australian CI providers have deficient IoT security skills and are insufficiently prepared to respond to CI incidents.

9.3. Annex D.3: Survey findings

The following points are based on a detailed analysis of information from the internal consultation survey. This survey identified gaps in existing solutions for Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR). It provided a comprehensive list of capability needs and gaps.

Technologies and tools that can help close these gaps will aid in preventing, detecting, and mitigating threats to critical infrastructures, including cyber-attacks, physical attacks, and natural disasters. Utilizing advanced technologies can enhance the resilience and continuity of these systems, protecting society from severe disruptions.

Figure Annex D.6 illustrates the EU-CIP survey findings on technologies that could address existing capability gaps. In line with identified gaps, solutions like cyber-physical threat intelligence, security risk assessment, and modeling of cascading effects were seen as the most promising for mitigating these issues. Integrated security approaches and management of cascading effects were highlighted

as key capabilities needed for effective CIP/CIR systems.

Adaptive threat hunting	9
Anomaly Detection	13
Biometric Authentication	1
Blockchain/DLT Technology	3
Closed Circuit Television Systems	4
Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence	17
Cybersecurity Tools	12
Data Loss Prevention Technology	8
Digital twins	13
Disinformation Management	6
End-Point Protection	5
Image Analysis	5
Impact assessment tools	14
Machine Learning – Pattern Det...	10
Modelling of cascading effects a...	12
Pentesting	9
Security Information and Event ...	7
Security Risk Assessment	16
Social Media Analysis	4
Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	5
Visual Scene Analysis	3
Sandboxes	1
Social Graph Analysis	2
Surveillance Systems	7
Malware Detection	11
Ransomware	7
5G Communications – Internet ...	8
Altro	4

Figure 10: State of the Art Technologies

The technological solutions in question are geared towards thwarting a variety of threats, encompassing cyber-attacks, physical intrusions, and natural disasters. The gamut of tools encompasses advanced cybersecurity technologies that arm against cyber threats, while physical security technologies enhance deterrence and detection. Notably, predictive analytics and machine learning are emerging as potent tools for identifying vulnerabilities and enabling pre-emptive mitigation measures. This cutting-edge technology is fundamentally pivotal in fortifying the resilience of CI systems, fending off the potentially catastrophic consequences of their compromise.

In an intriguing parallel, the EU-CIP project's internal survey and member feedback spotlighted trends that echo these technological considerations. The resounding resonance among these trends with the previously mentioned technologies is striking. In particular, cyber-physical threat

intelligence emerges as a salient trend, complemented by collaborative threat intelligence and predictive security measures. Figure Annex D-7 illustrates some of the trending CIP/CIR technologies according to the internal survey of the project and the feedback of EU-CIP members.

Figure 11: Important Trends in CIP/CIR domain

The results of the trends survey are in-line with the above-listed technologies. Specifically, cyber-physical threat intelligence represents one of the most important trends followed by collaborative threat intelligence and predictive security.

Emanating from the EU-CIP survey is a technological narrative that resonates with the identified gaps. A core array of technologies captures the limelight for their potential to ameliorate the existing gaps. Integrating these technologies addresses the dearth of holistic security approaches and the comprehensive handling of cascading effects, emblematic of the current limitations within the CIP/CIR systems.

Of paramount significance, a core group of state-of-the-art technologies surfaces as the most pertinent for bridging the gaps in CIP and CIR:

1. **Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence**
2. **Security Risk Assessment**
3. **Impact Assessment Tools**
4. **Digital Twins**
5. **Anomaly Detection**
6. **Cybersecurity Tools**
7. **Modelling of Cascading Effects and Interdependencies between CIs**

The incorporation of advanced technologies such as Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence, Security Risk Assessment, Impact Assessment Tools, Digital Twins, Anomaly Detection, Cybersecurity Tools, and the Modelling of Cascading Effects and Interdependencies between CIs can substantially contribute to addressing the identified capability gaps within the domain of CIP (see Annex C).

- Firstly, in addressing **CG1 - Poor Automation**, these technologies can play a pivotal role. Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence and Anomaly Detection systems can provide real-time threat data and promptly trigger automated responses when potential threats are identified. By leveraging Digital Twins, organizations can simulate automated responses to cyber-attacks and ensure that security controls are automatically verified, diagnosed, and rectified. Furthermore, the adoption of Artificial Intelligence within Cybersecurity Tools enables the automation of threat detection and mitigation processes, substantially enhancing the automation loop's efficiency and closing the gap associated with manual interventions.
- Moving to **CG2 - Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness**, Digital Twins, when deployed effectively, can offer a holistic view of interconnected assets and their dependencies. They can model and visualize the complexities of interdependencies, aiding in creating security policies that account for these factors. Additionally, Security Risk Assessment and Impact Assessment Tools can help in evaluating interconnectedness risks comprehensively, addressing the challenge of limited control over interconnected assets.
- For **CG3 - Poor Alignment of Resilience Indicators**, advanced technologies like Modelling of Cascading Effects can help standardize resilience indicators and align them across different CI sectors. These models can provide a common framework for assessing and managing resilience indicators, improving the overall alignment of such indicators.
- Regarding **CG4 - Lack of agreed Standards-based stress-testing procedures**, the adoption of standardized stress-testing procedures can be facilitated through digital platforms. Digital Twins can replicate infrastructural scenarios for stress testing, while Cybersecurity Tools can ensure the security of the procedures themselves.
- When addressing **CG5 - Problems with the classification of IoT Devices**, advanced technology can offer solutions such as Machine Learning algorithms for classifying IoT devices based on their behaviour and characteristics. This can aid in creating tailored security measures for different IoT classes, moving away from the current one-size-fits-all approach.
- In tackling **CG6 - Scalability in the Mitigation of DDoS attacks**, technologies like AI and Machine Learning can enable more adaptive and dynamic DDoS mitigation strategies. These technologies can detect and respond to novel DDoS attack methods, including those exploiting IoT devices and AI bots.
- Concerning **CG7 - Development and Deployment of AI-based systems**, embracing AI technologies within CIP/CIR solutions is crucial. AI-powered threat detection systems can intelligently identify attack patterns, while it's equally important to develop safeguards against potential vulnerabilities introduced by generative AI systems, thus balancing innovation with security.
- To address **CG8 - Lack of Holistic Security Management Systems**, advanced technologies can offer holistic solutions that are adaptable to various stakeholders. Digital Twins can be used to model security management systems that are tailored to different CI sectors while maintaining uniformity.
- For **CG9 - Gaps in Emergency Management Processes**, digital platforms can facilitate standardized communication processes. Advanced communication systems can be developed, incorporating AI for efficient information sharing with external entities and public authorities during emergencies.
- In response to **CG10 - Inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats**, dynamic solutions can be developed, integrating adaptive AI technologies. AI models can continuously evolve their threat detection capabilities by learning from emerging threats, ensuring proactive responses to evolving threats.

- Considering **CG11 - Poor Awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges**, the use of immersive training technologies can increase awareness and preparedness among security teams. Virtual simulations and training scenarios can help personnel better understand interconnected infrastructures, cascading effects, and the intricacies of modern CIP/CIR challenges.
- For **CG12 - Adaptive Threat Intelligence**: The development and adoption of cutting-edge technologies like AI and machine learning are instrumental in addressing this gap. These technologies enable the continuous monitoring and analysis of rapidly evolving threats, allowing for the real-time adaptation of threat intelligence mechanisms. AI-powered threat intelligence systems can identify and analyse emerging threat vectors, tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) used by sophisticated threat actors. By leveraging machine learning algorithms, these systems can identify patterns and anomalies in real-time, providing critical insights to enhance defences and adapt to evolving threats promptly.
- Moving on to **CG13 - Incident Response Coordination**: The implementation of standardized incident response protocols and the use of digital platforms for coordination can bridge this gap. Emerging technologies like blockchain can facilitate secure and transparent incident response coordination across multiple CI entities and government agencies. Blockchain's immutable ledger ensures the integrity of incident data, while smart contracts can automate certain response actions, streamlining coordination during crises. Additionally, cloud-based incident response platforms can provide a centralized hub for real-time communication, information sharing, and task assignment, promoting a unified approach to responding to cyber incidents and threats across the CI landscape.
- For **CG14 - Emerging Technology Adoption**: Embracing emerging technologies is key to enhancing CIP. AI, quantum computing, and blockchain can be integrated into protection strategies to fortify security and resilience. AI can power advanced threat detection and predictive analytics, while quantum computing can bolster encryption and decryption capabilities, rendering critical data more secure. Blockchain technology can ensure the integrity of CI transactions and communications, enhancing trust and transparency. Encouraging the adoption of these technologies, along with regulatory support and incentives, can expedite their integration into CIP strategies.
- Lastly, regarding **CG15 - Rapid Recovery Strategies**: Emerging technologies play a pivotal role in developing and implementing rapid recovery strategies. Digital Twins can simulate various incident scenarios, allowing organizations to test and refine recovery plans proactively. AI and machine learning can automate the restoration of critical systems and processes, minimizing downtime. Additionally, blockchain's resilience and fault tolerance can be leveraged to ensure data integrity during recovery efforts. Rapid recovery strategies should be integrated into overall incident response plans, focusing on swift restoration to minimize the impact of incidents on CI operations. These strategies should be regularly tested and updated to adapt to evolving threats and technologies.

Emerging technologies like **Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and cybersecurity automation** hold immense promise in addressing the identified gaps within CIP. Emerging technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and cybersecurity automation offer a multifaceted approach to addressing the array of capability gaps within CIP.

- Beginning with **CG1 - Poor Automation**, AI and IoT play pivotal roles in enhancing automation by enabling fast detection, threat protection, and recovery. AI-powered systems can rapidly identify and respond to cyber threats, leveraging machine learning algorithms to adapt security controls in real-time. IoT devices can collect vast amounts of data for threat

monitoring and assist in implementing security policies efficiently. The integration of these technologies can help bridge the gap in achieving automation while complying with evolving regulations.

- For **CG2 - Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness**, IoT technologies are central to improving control over interconnected assets and dependencies. IoT sensors can provide real-time insights into the status and performance of critical infrastructure components, facilitating a holistic CIP approach. Novel security knowledge modelling approaches and interoperability solutions can further enhance control by standardizing how diverse assets are interconnected, ensuring comprehensive security policies are implemented.
- Addressing **CG3 - Poor Alignment of Resilience Indicators and CG4 - Lack of agreed Standards-based stress-testing procedures**, AI and data analytics can assist in aligning resilience indicators and developing standardized stress-testing procedures. AI can analyse diverse resilience indicators, align them, and provide insights for a structured CIR approach. Additionally, AI-driven simulations can help formulate stress-testing procedures based on real-world scenarios, ensuring that critical infrastructure systems are tested comprehensively.
- For **CG5 - Problems with the classification of IoT Devices**, AI, and machine learning can be employed to improve the identification and classification of IoT-based assets. These technologies can automatically categorize and profile IoT devices, considering their diversity and complexity, thus enhancing security strategies tailored to each class of device.
- Regarding **CG6 - Scalability in the Mitigation of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks**, IoT devices and AI can collaborate to mitigate these attacks effectively. IoT devices can detect unusual traffic patterns, while AI-driven algorithms can identify sophisticated DDoS attack vectors and orchestrate timely responses, making the mitigation scalable and adaptive.
- Moving to **CG7 - Development and Deployment of AI-based systems**, embracing AI technologies is crucial for unlocking their potential in CIP/CIR solutions. Proper training and awareness programs can ensure that employees and vendors understand AI capabilities and limitations. Moreover, AI systems can be developed to address new adaptive AI-driven cyberattacks, emphasizing the importance of proactive AI integration.
- In addressing **CG8 - Lack of Holistic Security Management Systems**, the integration of AI and IoT into security management platforms can provide holistic solutions. These technologies offer uniformity and automation, ensuring operational applicability across various stakeholders and promoting standardized security management practices.
- For **CG9 - Gaps in Emergency Management Processes**, emerging technologies can facilitate standardized processes through real-time communication, data sharing, and automation. Blockchain technology can provide a secure and transparent communication channel, while AI-powered chatbots can assist in handling emergency communications with external entities and public authorities.
- Regarding **CG10 - Inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats**, AI and machine learning are essential for proactively identifying and adapting to evolving threats. They can analyse vast datasets to detect emerging threat patterns and continuously update knowledge models to stay ahead of the evolving threat landscape.
- Considering **CG11 - Poor Awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges**, training programs and awareness initiatives can leverage AI and digital platforms for disseminating information about contemporary challenges and promoting a cultural shift towards embracing interconnected infrastructures and cascading effects as crucial considerations in CIP.
- Addressing **CG12 - Adaptive Threat Intelligence**, emerging technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning need to play a pivotal role. These technologies can

continuously monitor and analyse the evolving threat landscape in real-time. AI-driven threat intelligence mechanisms can adapt rapidly to emerging threat vectors and identify new tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs) used by increasingly sophisticated threat actors. Machine learning algorithms can discern patterns and anomalies in data, facilitating early threat detection and enabling security teams to respond proactively. This adaptive approach to threat intelligence is critical for safeguarding CI as it ensures that security measures are always aligned with the latest threat landscape.

- For **CG13 - Incident Response Coordination**, emerging technologies offer solutions to enhance coordination among multiple CI entities and government agencies. Blockchain, for instance, can provide a secure and transparent platform for sharing incident-related information and ensuring data integrity. AI can facilitate the automation of incident response processes, including the orchestration of actions across various stakeholders. Standardized incident response protocols can be developed with AI-driven decision support systems that guide responders through crisis situations. These technologies collectively contribute to a well-structured and unified approach to incident response in the CI landscape.
- Regarding **CG14 - Emerging Technology Adoption**, ironically, emerging technologies themselves can help bridge this gap. By embracing AI, quantum computing, and blockchain, CIP strategies can become more robust and resilient. AI can enhance threat detection and response, quantum computing can bolster encryption and decryption capabilities, and blockchain can ensure the integrity and traceability of critical data. The hesitancy in adopting these technologies may stem from concerns about their novelty and potential vulnerabilities. However, with careful planning, regulations, and awareness programs, these technologies can be safely integrated into strategies aimed at safeguarding CI.
- Finally, for **CG15 - Rapid Recovery Strategies**, AI and IoT can be instrumental in developing effective and swift recovery plans. AI can analyse the impact of incidents on CI components and recommend optimal recovery strategies. IoT devices can provide real-time data on the status of infrastructure elements, facilitating a rapid assessment of the damage. By automating certain recovery tasks, AI can expedite the restoration of operations, minimizing downtime and reducing the impact of incidents. Rapid recovery strategies should be an integral part of CIP, complementing the focus on prevention and detection to ensure overall resilience.

10. Annex E: Roadmap for filling the gaps

Following the identification of gaps that European CI are facing, EU-CIP proposes some actions to be undertaken within R&D, specifically in terms of the development of required technologies, all of which will be flanked by specific and tailored policy actions.

These actions are listed in the following implementation plan and will be further elaborated upon in upcoming EU-CIP roadmap documents. Furthermore, EU-CIP suggests some good practices to monitor and evaluate the implementation of the roadmap based on the actions which should be taken.

10.1. Annex E.1: Implementation plan

The actions identified by EU-CIP for the roadmap implementation to achieve a more resilient CIP/CIR landscape can be found in the following.

10.1.1. Annex E.1.1: R&D actions

- Research & Development Programs in areas that fill-in the identified gaps, including the following areas (see Annex C):
 - Knowledge Modelling for Interconnected Infrastructures.
 - Dynamic Threat Modelling and Adaptive Threat Intelligence.
 - Frameworks of Resilience Indicators.
 - CIP Automation Technologies including AI and IoT systems for cybersecurity.
 - Artificial Intelligence Systems for Early Preparedness and Proactive cybersecurity.
 - IoT Devices classifications.
 - Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence.
 - Systems for Supply Chain Security.
- Development/production of research prototypes in the above areas (TRL between 3 and 6).
- Creation of detailed research plans for each one of the identified research areas, including further analysis of research gaps and challenges, as well as the documentation of candidate research solutions/approaches.
- Collaboration between research centres and CI operators for the validation of research solutions.
- Support for research funding programs, including collaborative research and grants.
- Measures and programs for research collaborations at regional, national, and EU levels.

- Inclusion of the above-listed research topics in the research agendas of existing centres of excellence and/or of innovation hubs.
- Establishment of centres of excellence focusing on the above discussed research areas.

10.1.2. Annex E.1.2: Technology development actions

- Development of prototypes of innovative products or services leveraging research results in areas that fill the identified gaps (TRL between 5 and 7).
- Field validation of prototypes under real-life conditions.
- Design and implementation of production-ready solutions.
- Positioning of technological solutions against the technological state of the art, including competing products and services in the CIP market.
- Investment in innovative CIP/CIR processes leveraging the developed technologies.
- Protection of knowledge through patents.

10.1.3. Annex E.1.3: Policy actions

- Auditing compliance to existing directives.
- Design of funding programs to support R&I activities in the identified areas.
- Actions to support training and skills development for individual organizations.

10.2. Annex E.2: Monitoring and evaluation

In order to supervise the implementation actions of the roadmap, some good practices to monitor and evaluate the progress are listed below.

- Monitoring of the actions against KPIs, including:
 - The number and type of technologies developed.
 - The number and type of research prototypes produced.
 - The number and type of innovative products produced.
 - The number and type of innovative products validated.
 - The number and type of innovative products deployed in production.
 - The number and type of innovative products commercialized.
 - Professionals and stakeholders trained/upskilled.

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